

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Rome, May 8, 2023

CNR Headquarters (Marconi Room)
Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, Rome, Italy

Conference Proceedings

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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

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Scientific Program

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	Polar analytes and large panels, is there necessarily a need to rely to extreme solutions? A reflection on going back to basic	

15:20	Antonio Triolo (Menarini, Firenze).....	149
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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

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Giulia Mazzocanti (Università di Roma La Sapienza)
Frontiers in chromatography: Insights into chiral separations

Frontiers in chromatography: insights into chiral separations

Giulia MAZZOCCANTI

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Chiral separations play a crucial role in analysing complex molecules with stereogenic elements. However, sometimes more sophisticated techniques are necessary. In this contribution, several powerful tools for resolving various issues in natural product chemistry, asymmetric synthesis, and chiral tuning control of biopharmaceutical synthesis are described.

One problem is that often the minor enantiomer or racemate of chiral natural products may be unavailable as a reference sample and difficult to synthesize. To address this issue, we developed the Inverted Chirality Columns Approach (ICCA), which allows for identifying an enantiomeric couple in a complex mixture and enantiomeric trace analysis. ICCA, based on synthetic selector-based columns (such as WhelkO1), can be helpful in determining the enantiomeric purity of naturally occurring samples and evaluating the stereochemical efficiency of enantioselective synthetic pathways. We demonstrated the applicability of ICCA in identifying all four stereoisomers of the cannabinoid Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ^9 -THC) as natural products [1]. Our results showed that the natural (-)- Δ^9 -*trans*-THC has an extreme enantiomeric excess (i.e., 99.7%) and Δ^9 -*cis*-THC is scalemic, and its major enantiomer was characterized as a partial cannabinoid agonist in vitro and elicited a full tetrad response in mice at 50 mg/kg doses [2]. We suggest that the legal discrimination between narcotic and non-narcotic cannabis varieties based on the contents of " Δ^9 -THC and isomers" needs revision to account for the presence of Δ^9 -*cis*-THCs in cannabis fiber hemp varieties. Additionally, we discuss the chiral analysis of Cannabichromene (CBC), which occurs as a scalemate with strain-dependent composition in terms of both enantiomeric excess and enantiomeric dominance. Investigating the biological profile of both enantiomers of CBC is essential to assess the contribution of this compound to the activity of Cannabis preparations [3].

The biopharmaceutical industry also faces challenges in controlling the enantiomeric purity of reagents and intermediate products in the solid-phase synthesis of therapeutic peptides. To respond to this need, we developed a method for resolving 31 racemates of N α -Fmoc amino acids using zwitterionic-teicoplanin chiral stationary phases (CSPs). The CSPs were prepared by covalently bonding the teicoplanin selector on fully-porous particles and superficially-porous particles of narrow dispersion particle-size distribution. The zwitterionic CSP prepared on superficially-porous particles exhibited superior enantioselectivity and resolution compared to that made of fully porous particles. This study provides a solution for the rapid determination of enantiomeric excess of N α -Fmoc amino acids, indeed the use of a short column packed with zwitterionic teicoplanin allows separation in the second scale. The use of either acetonitrile- or methanol-rich mobile phases allows for flexibility in balancing speed and enantioresolution [4]. Additionally, we discuss the challenges in controlling the epimeric purity of glucagon, a therapeutic peptide used to treat severe hypoglycemia, due to various modifications during production [5]. The use of hydrophobic positively charged ion pair agents in the mobile phase, such as TBA, mitigates unwanted interactions and produces symmetrical peaks for

analysis and enhancing diastereoselectivity. The elution mode thus developed called dynamic electrostatic repulsion reversed phase (d-ERRP) has proved to be an effective and reliable technique for the control of peptides of pharmaceutical interest [6].

References:

- [1] Mazzocanti, G., et al. *Chemical communication* (2017): 12262-12265.
- [2] Schafroth, M. A., et al. *Journal of natural products* 84.9 (2021): 2502-2510.
- [3] Calcaterra, A., et al. *Journal of Natural Products* (2023).
- [4] Mazzocanti, G., et al. *Journal of Chromatography A* 1624 (2020): 461235.
- [5] Mazzocanti, G., et al. *RSC advances* 10.21 (2020): 12604-12610.
- [6] Mazzocanti, G., et al. *Molecules* 26.14 (2021): 4348.

Frontiers in chromatography: insights into chiral separation

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Department of Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Technologies

Sapienza University of Rome

“Extreme Chromatography Workshop”

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

8th May 2023

SAPIENZA
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Italian Mass Spectrometry Society

Introduction: Enantioselective chromatography and thermodynamic meaning

* ϕ represents the volume phase ratio of stationary and mobile phase (V_s/V_m) which is equal to $\phi = (1 - \epsilon)/\epsilon$ wherein ϵ is the total porosity of the column

The K_S and K_R describe the equilibrium constants of the process, and the transient diastereomers can be discriminated based on their difference in free energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{R-S}$)

Retention factor:

$$k_{R(S)} = K_{R(S)} \phi^*$$

$$\ln k_{R(S)} = \ln K_{R(S)} + \ln \phi = -\frac{\Delta G_{R(S)}}{RT} + \ln \phi = -\frac{\Delta H_{R(S)}}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S_{R(S)}}{R} + \ln \phi$$

$$\Delta G_{R(S)} = -RT \ln k_{R(S)}$$

Enantioselectivity factor:

$$\alpha = \frac{k_{2^{nd} \text{ eluted}}}{k_{1^{st} \text{ eluted}}}$$

$$\Delta\Delta G_{R-S} = -RT \ln \alpha \rightarrow \ln \alpha = -\frac{\Delta\Delta G_{R-S}}{RT} = -\frac{\Delta\Delta H_{R-S}}{RT} + \frac{\Delta\Delta S_{R-S}}{R}$$

Introduction: What is meant by kinetics?

High surface area in sub-2 μm silica particles is necessary to obtain comparable loading (micromoles per gram) and density (micromoles per m^2) of the selector to that achieved on the 3 or 5 μm fully porous silica particles.

Same k and α , the increase in R_s is due only to the increase in N

Non-porous fused silica core surrounded by a porous crust, whose volume is around 65% of the total particle volume.

Advantages:

- i) a lower term A of van Deemter equation, since the 2.7 μm SPPs generally pack better than the sub-2 μm FPPs,
- ii) a low longitudinal diffusion (i.e., term B);
- iii) a fast mass transfer.

Smaller surface area, thermodynamic variations are passing from a CSP based on FPP to one on SPP

3

Chiral stationary phases: High molecular weight vs low-medium molecular weight selectors

Chiral stationary phases (CSPs) can be distinguished based on the molecular weight of the chiral selector

4

Pirkle-type chiral selectors

- Simple organic compounds (1 or 2 chiral centres) and low MW, capable of giving multiple interactions
- Bulky groups for the conformational control of the interaction
- The stationary phases based on Pirkle-type selectors are stable and have a high loading capacity. They are used for the resolution of mixtures of enantiomers both at the analytical and preparative level
- **Totally synthetic, so their configuration is defined**

1989 Gasparrini et al.

1992 Pirkle et al.

Interesting application of Pirkle-type based CSPs

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products

(S)-Camptothecin derivatives

Phytocannabinoids

Control of products from asymmetric synthesis and pharmaceuticals

3-methyl-4-phenyl-nitropentan-2-one

Ruxolitinib

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products

Vegetable extracts are highly enriched complex mixtures

Often the minor enantiomers or the racemates, are not available as reference samples

ICCA

Inverted Chirality Columns Approach

"REVERSAL ORDER OF THE PEAK ELUTION FOR ENANTIOMERICALLY ENRICHED SELECTANDS BY INVERTING THE CHIRALITY OF THE SELECTOR IS A USEFUL DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR VERIFYING AN ENANTIOMER SEPARATION BUT IT MAY ALSO HAVE AN IMPORTANT ROLE IN QUANTITATIVE ENANTIOMER ANALYSIS"

F. Gasparrini et al. Anal. Chem. 2007, 79, 6013

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products

Inverted Chirality Columns Approach

ICCA

Racemic sample

Enantiomeric chiral stationary phases (CSPs)

(+)-CSP

Chemical
(retention, selectivity)
and
geometrical
(dimensions, particle size, packing efficiency, etc.)
equivalency

(-)-CSP

Detection

Identical chromatographic behavior, but opposite stereochemical preferences for two enantiomeric species

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products

Inverted Chirality Columns Approach

Identification of enantiomeric couples and *e.e.* evaluation in complex mixtures, in the absence of the reference enantiomers and without chiroptical detection

(S)-Camptothecin

(S)-Camptothecin (CPT) is a potent antitumor alkaloid isolated from the Chinese tree *Camptotheca acuminata* by Wall *et al.* [*]

The camptothecin family drugs appears to have the unique mechanism of action to stabilize the binding of topoisomerase I (an enzyme involved in the maintenance of DNA topology) leading to DNA fragmentation.

[*] M.E. Wall, M.C. Wani, C.E. Cook, K.H. Palmer, A.T. McPhail, G.A. Sims, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 88 (1966) 3888-3890

(S)-Camptothecin promising derivatives

- Semi synthetic derivatives are obtained from camptothecin which is supposed to be a single pure enantiomer (*S* configuration at C-20)
- The synthetic pathway does not affect the stereogenic center
- The *S* configuration of CPT is maintained

FDA guidelines on chiral drugs require direct proofs !!

[*] S. Penco, L. Merlini, F. Zunino, P. Carminati, *International Patent*, n. WO 00/53607, priority date: 3.9.1999

GIMATECAN ENANTIOMERIC PURITY CONTROL Choosing the right CSP chirality for trace determination

GIMATECAN: EXTREME ENANTIOMERIC EXCESS DETERMINATION (Area ratio $\approx 1:50000$)

Sensitivity

LOD= 0.7 pg inj. (e.e. >99.995%)

LOQ= 2.2 pg inj.

Different Batch analysis

Sample	Batch number	R/S	Found e.e.%
ST1481	375/25	0.027	99.946
ST1481	375/79	0.045	99.910
ST1481	441/43	<0.002	>99.995
ST1481	375/97	0.024	99.952
ST1481	375/99	0.006	99.988
ST1481	532/66	<0.002	>99.995
ST1481	532/68	<0.002	>99.995
ST1481	532/70	<0.002	>99.995
ST1481	532/74	<0.002	>99.995

Extreme
e.e.

F. Gasparri, W. Cabri, E. Badaloni et al. *Anal. Chem.* 2007, 79, 6013

Chiral selectors on *sub-2_μm* silica particles

Whelk-O1 CSP

- a) Pirkle, W.H.; Welch, C.J.; Lamm, B. J. *Org. Chem.* 1992, 57, 3854.
 b) Pirkle, W.H.; Welch, C.J. *J. Liq. Chromatogr.* 1992, 15, 1947.

Totally porous silica

Thermo Synchronis 1.7 μm,
 pore size 120 Å, surface area 320 m² g⁻¹

Anal. Chem., 84 (15), (2012), 6805
J.C.A., 1269 (2012), 226

KINETIC PERFORMANCE

eHPLC vs. eUHPLC

$$H = A + \frac{B}{\mu} + C\mu$$

Column	H _{min} (μm)	h _{min} (l)	μ _{0,opt} (mm/s)	Φ (mL/min)	N/m
Regis 150x4.6 mm 5 μm	14.1 (14.5)	2.82 (2.90)	1.13 (1.13)	0.60 (0.60)	70 921 (68 965)
Regis 150x4.6 mm 3 μm	7.66 (8.71)	2.55 (2.90)	1.72 (1.47)	1.16 (1.00)	130 548 (114 810)
UHPLC-WhelkO1 100x4.6 mm 1.8 μm	4.13 (4.21)	2.29 (2.34)	2.99 (2.70)	2.00 (1.80)	242 130 (237 529)

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products: phytocannabinoids

Selector: Whelk-O1

Selectands

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products: Supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC)

- The main advantages of this technique, which has intermediate characteristics to GC and LC, are diffusion coefficients and viscosity midway between those of gases and liquids and, at high pressure, density close to liquids. These qualities result in **fast, high-efficiency separations, which may be achieved at a higher flow rate without the pressure drop observed in LC.**
- Supercritical CO₂ can be mixed with other solvents and additives, increasing the selectivity of the technique.

consumption of organic solvents decreases by 90% compared to NP-LC

Control of chromatographic equivalence of the columns with opposite chirality

Eluent: CO₂:MeOH 98:2; Flow rate: 3.5 mL/min; T_{col}: 30 °C; V_{inj}: 1 ml; UV @ 214nm
Sample: mixture of standards

Analysis of particularly elusive chiral natural products

* From Prof. Carreira's group (ETH Zurich)

Eluent: Isocratic condition A: CO₂, B: MeOH 98:2; Flow rate: 3.5 ml/min;
T_{col}: 30° C; V_{inj}: 1 μl UV detection 214nm

The "inverted chirality column approach" for unraveling the natural composition of Δ⁹-THC stereoisomers

Cannabis sativa L. - Drug type

Extreme e.e.

(-)-Δ⁹-trans-THC: ee > 99.7 %
Δ⁹-trans-THC / Δ⁹-cis-THC ratio : nd*
* The cis isomer is below LOD

Cannabis sativa L. - Fiber type

(-)-Δ⁹-cis-THC: ee ≈ 80 %
Δ⁹-trans-THC / Δ⁹-cis-THC ratio : 2.3

Bioactivity of Δ^9 -THC stereoisomers

In vitro CB1 and CB2 receptor functional activities in [³⁵S]GTP γ S binding assay (EC₅₀, nM)

	(-)- Δ^9 -trans-THC	(-)- Δ^9 -cis-THC	(+)- Δ^9 -cis-THC
CB1	43 ± 30 (partial) ^a	552 ± 123 (partial) ^a	>10 000
CB2	12 ± 7 (partial) ^a	119 ± 69 (partial) ^a	>10 000

^aPartial = partial agonist compared to the full agonist CP55940.

«Tetrad test» In vivo

(-)- Δ^9 -trans-THC (gray) and (-)- Δ^9 -cis-THC (green) compared with vehicle control (white) in BALB/c male mice 1 h after intraperitoneal injection.

All four stereoisomers of Δ^9 -THC are natural products, established thanks to ICCA.

The legal status of Δ^9 -cis-THC is, however, unclear. The current legal discrimination between narcotic and non-narcotic cannabis varieties focuses on the content of " Δ^9 -THC and isomers" and is based only on the achiral chromatographic (GC or HPLC) determination of Δ^9 - and Δ^8 -trans-tetrahydrocannabinol

Back cover
2017

Mazzocanti, G., Ismail, O. H., D'Acquarica, I., Villani, C., Manzo, C., Wilcox, M., ... & Gasparrini, F. (2017). Cannabis through the looking glass: chemo-and enantio-selective separation of phytocannabinoids by enantioselective ultra high performance supercritical fluid chromatography. *Chemical Communications*, 53(91), 12262-12265.

Front cover
Editor's choice
Free open access
2021

Schafroth, M. A., Mazzocanti, G., Reynoso-Moreno, I., Erni, R., Pollastro, F., Caprioglio, D., ... & Appendino, G. (2021). Δ^9 -cis-Tetrahydrocannabinol: Natural Occurrence, Chirality, and Pharmacology. *Journal of natural products*, 84(9), 2502-2510.

Cannabichromene

Cannabis sativa L.-Drug type

Table 1 Determination of the enantiomeric excess (ee) for "THC" (4) and CBC (5) in the Bedrocan[®] ethanolic extract on the UHPC-Whelk-O1 sub-2 μm columns under eUHPSFC conditions

CSP config.	Peak name	Area (μV s)	EF ^a (%)	ee (%)
(R,R)	(-)-4	3 694 825	— ^b	— ^b
(R,R)	(+)-4	— ^b	— ^b	— ^b
(S,S)	(+)-4	4917	0.13 ₅	99.73
(S,S)	(-)-4	3 642 648	99.86 ₅	—
(R,R)	[CD(-)280]-5 ^c	18 766	37.42	25.16
(R,R)	[CD(+280)-5 ^c	31 383	62.58	—
(S,S)	[CD(+280)-5 ^c	31 346	62.81	25.62
(S,S)	[CD(-)280]-5 ^c	18 559	37.19	—

^a EF = enantiomeric fraction. ^b On the (R,R)-Whelk-O1 column the (+)-4 peak is eluting on the tailing of the major (-)-4 component and thus it is not quantifiable. ^c Plus and minus signs refer to the signs of the circular dichroism (CD) band at the indicated wavelength.

Mazzocanti, G., Ismail, O. H., D'Acquarica, I., Villani, C., Manzo, C., Wilcox, M., ... & Gasparrini, F. (2017). Cannabis through the looking glass: chemo- and enantio-selective separation of phytocannabinoids by enantioselective ultra high performance supercritical fluid chromatography. *Chemical Communications*, 53(91), 12262-12265.

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Cannabichromene

Chromatograms (UV and CD traces) NP-eHPLC of CBC isolated fractions

Calcaterra, A., Cianfoni, G., Tortora, C., Manetto, S., Grassi, G., Botta, B., Gasparrini F., Mazzocanti G., Appendino, G. (2023). Natural Cannabichromene (CBC) Shows Distinct Scalemicity Grades and Enantiomeric Dominance in Cannabis sativa Strains. *Journal of Natural Products*.

Figure S3. Chromatograms on (S,S)-WhelkO1 (A) and (R,R)-WhelkO1 (B) column of CBC purified fraction from Finola (black-traces), Orange (green-traces), Carmagnola AZ Greenlake (Blue-traces) and OGM1 C37 (red-traces) cultivars. Detection UV and CD at 280 nm.

Control of products from asymmetric synthesis and pharmaceuticals

Scheme 1. Scheme of reaction for the preparation of the 3-methyl-4-phenyl-5-nitropentan-2-one (3).

Fig. 2. Chromatographic profile of 3 enantiomers obtained with A) (R,R)-Whelk O1 column (CSP 1), B) (S,S)-Whelk O1 column (CSP 2) and C) tandem-columns (CSP 1 plus CSP 2) arrangement. Experimental conditions: eluent, water/ACN-60/40 (v/v), flow-rate, 1.0 mL/min; column temperature, 25 °C, wavelength of detection, 220 nm.

"In the present paper, we have clearly demonstrated that the ICCA method can be successfully applied to monitor the outcome of enantioselective synthesis protocols even in the absence of pure enantiomeric standards."

Ianni, F., Tiecco, M., Carotti, A., Pucciarini, L., Saluti, G., Galarini, R., ... & Natalini, B. (2019). Application of the "inverted chirality columns approach" for the monitoring of asymmetric synthesis protocols. *Talanta*, 203, 147-152.

Control of products from asymmetric synthesis and pharmaceuticals

Figure 3. Enantioselective analysis of (a) ruxolitinib phosphate standard with chiral stationary phase (CSP) 1 (solid line) and CSP 2 (dotted line), according to the inverted chirality columns approach (ICCA)

Figure 1. Structure of ruxolitinib, (3R)-3-cyclopentyl-3-[4-(7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)pyrazol-1-yl]propanenitrile.

Di Michele, A.; Schoubben, A.; Varfaj, I.; D'Arpino, A.; Micolini, L.; Sardella, R.; Ricci, M.; Tiacchi, E. Improved Achiral and Chiral HPLC-UV Analysis of Ruxolitinib in Two Different Drug Formulations. *Separations* 2020, 7, 47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations7030047>

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Teicoplanin-based CSP

Macrocytic glycopeptides are highly popular as chiral stationary phases (CSPs) in HPLC due to the wide applicability for the resolution of many classes of racemates (a-, b- and g-amino acids and peptides, b-blockers, b-agonists, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory etc.). The unique structure of macrocytic glycopeptides (semi-rigid peptide basket aglycone and surrounding sugars) ensures different interactive sites (e.g., hydrophobic pockets, -OH, -NH₂ and -COOH groups, halogen atoms, aromatic moieties). The commercially available HPLC-Chirobiotic⁽¹⁾ phases afford good efficiency, high reproducibility and long-term stability in reversed-phase, polar organic and polar ionic modes, sub-critical fluid chromatography, normal-phase.

Chiral Selector : Teicoplanin A2_2

Zwitterionic teicoplanin-based CSP

The commercially available HPLC-Chirobiotic phases offer good efficiency, high reproducibility and long-term stability in the modes: reverse phase, organic polar, ionic polar, supercritical fluid chromatography, normal phase

Zwitterionic Teicoplanin-based CSP was developed from totally porous and monodisperse silica particles, sub-2 µm (totally porous mono-dispersed Titan silica with particle diameter of 1.9 µm, pore size 120 Å and surface area equal to 282 m² / g).

O.H. Ismail *et al.*, J. Chromatogr., A, 2016, 1427, 55–68

UHPC-Tzwitt-Titan 120Å 1.9 µm vs. Chirobiotic T2 5 µm

UHPC-Tzwitt-Titan 120Å 1.9 µm 100x4.6 mm 1.9 µm Chirobiotic T2 250x4.6 mm 5 µm

RP-UHPLC: MeOH/H₂O 85:15 + 20mM ammonium acetate
POM-UHPLC: ACN/MeOH 60:40, v/v + 0.055% CH₃COOH/0.03% TEA

UHPC-Tzwitt-Titan 120Å 1.9 µm – Ultra-fast chiral separations

Column geometry: 1.0 x 0.46 cm 1.9 µm

Column: UHPC-Titan120-Chirobiotic-Tzwitt-1.9, 1.0 x 0.46 cm, T: 35°C
RP-UHPLC: flow-rate: 2.0 mL/min; MeOH/H₂O 85:15 + 20mM ammonium acetate
HILIC-UHPLC: flow-rate: 2.0 mL/min; ACN/H₂O 85:15, v/v + 15mM ammonium acetate
POM-UHPLC: flow-rate: 2.0 mL/min; ACN/MeOH 60:40, v/v + 0.055% CH₃COOH/0.03% TEA
UHPSFC: flow-rate: 4.0 mL/min; CO₂/A 60:40; A: MeOH/H₂O 98:2 + 20mM CH₃COONH₄
NP-UHPLC: flow-rate: 2.0 mL/min; hexane (EtOH/MeOH 80:20) 50:50

Silica particles technology – FPPs and SPPs

Fully Porous Particles (FPPs)

Superficially porous particles (SPPs)

Ismail, O. H., Antonelli, M., Ciogli, A., Villani, C., Cavazzini, A., Catani, M., ... & Gasparrini, F. (2017). Future perspectives in high efficient and ultrafast chiral liquid chromatography through zwitterionic teicoplanin-based 2- μm superficially porous particles. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1520, 91-102.

van Deemter analyses – Chiral solute

2-(4-Chloro-phenoxy)-propionic acid

Halo 2.0 μm 100x4.6 mm

Sample	k' (/)	H_{min} (μm)	h_{min} (/)	N/m	Flow-rate _{opt} (mL/min)
1 st enantiomer	2.21	3.42	1.71	292 220	0.9
2 nd enantiomer	2.80	3.60	1.80	278 060	0.7

Halo 2.7 μm 100x4.6 mm

Sample	k' (/)	H_{min} (μm)	h_{min} (/)	N/m	Flow-rate _{opt} (mL/min)
Enantiomer 1	2.09	4.74	1.76	211 060	0.5
Enantiomer 2	2.88	5.16	1.91	193 720	0.5

Titan 1.9 μm 100x4.6 mm

Sample	k' (/)	H_{min} (μm)	h_{min} (/)	N/m	Flow-rate _{opt} (mL/min)
1 st enantiomer	2.61	3.82	2.01	261 950	0.7
2 nd enantiomer	3.29	4.00	2.11	249 900	0.6

Dionex Ultimate 3000RS
Eluent: ACN/H₂O 85:15 + 20mM HCOONH₄
T: 35°C

High speed/Ultra-High performance separations – 5-cm columns

Flow-rate: 1.0 mL/min

Flow-rate: 6.0 mL/min

Speed gain:

x6

Column geometry: 50x4.6 mm L.x.I.D.

Dionex Ultimate 3000RS

Eluent: ACN/H₂O 85:15 + 20mM HCOONH₄

T: 35°C

Ultra-fast/Ultra-High performance separations – 2-cm columns

Trend in the pharmaceutical market: the advent of therapeutic polypeptides and proteins

1982: the first insulin using rDNA technology were marketed.

Biological medicinal products : "a protein or nucleic acid-based pharmaceutical substance used for therapeutic or in vivo diagnostic purposes which is produced by means other than direct extraction from a native biological source". **European Medicines Agency (EMA)**

Polypeptides obtained by chemical synthesis : advantages

1. Useful for therapeutic peptides (no tertiary or quaternary structure)
2. Overcome the limitations of molecular biology (i.e., production of a single proteoform).
3. Lower number of purification steps

Polypeptides obtained by chemical synthesis: **critical point I**

- I. **Ultra-fast determination of enantiomeric excess (e.e.)** of N α -protected amino acids chiral synthons must be carefully evaluated.

Samples Analyzed:

32 N α -FMOC amino acids
(12 also protected on side chain *)

NEUTRAL-NONPOLAR AMINOACID

HILIC

COLUMN	k'	α	Rs	As	N/m
Tzwitt_Titan_FPP_50x4.6mm 1.9 μ m_120Å	2.11			1.13	232000
	2.51	1.19	2.88	1.31	138000
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.0 μ m_90Å	2.77			1.37	224780
	3.87	1.43	4.96	1.43	68900
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.7 μ m_160Å	4.22			1.21	177980
	6.05	1.43	5.27	1.33	70000
Teicoshell_100x4.6 mm 2.7 μ m_120 Å	0.75			0.95	355080
	0.88	1.16	2.16	1.04	286660

FMOC-D,L-Ala

ANP

COLUMN	k'	α	Rs	As	N/m
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.0 μ m_90Å	7.97			1.35	188340
	17.73	2.20	10.90	1.52	55160

BASIC AMINOACID

HILIC

COLUMN	k'	α	Rs	As	N/m
Tzwitt_Titan_FPP_50x4.6mm 1.9 μ m_120Å	5.78			n.a.	177040
	6.11	1.06	n.a.	n.a.	
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.0 μ m_90Å	6.09			1.51	162480
	6.89	1.13	2.25	1.44	126740
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.7 μ m_160Å	14.30			1.40	145900
	16.49	1.15	2.65	1.41	110480
Teicoshell_100x4.6 mm 2.7 μ m_120 Å	3.44			1.13	230200
	4.00	1.16	2.75	1.50	133620

FMOC-D,L-His

ANP

COLUMN	k'	α	Rs	As	N/m
Tzwitt_Halo_SPP_50x4.6mm 2.0 μ m_90Å	9.43			n.a.	83880
	14.86	1.58	2.70	1.50	78740

* Chemical impurity

...and let us make some considerations

The term *Resolution (Rs)* describes, in the chromatographic process, how well an analyte is separated from another, according to the equation:

$$R_s = \frac{\sqrt{N}}{4} \frac{(\alpha - 1)}{\alpha} \frac{k}{(k + 1)}$$

It depends on two thermodynamic factors: k is the measure of retention, namely retention factor, and α is the selectivity factor

$$k = \frac{t_R - t_0}{t_0} \quad \alpha = \frac{k_A}{k_B}$$

moreover, a kinetic one: N is the efficiency, concerning the number of theoretical plates

$$N = \frac{L}{H}$$

Bar Charts

Case study: Glucagon

29 AAs, 4 basic aminoacids

Mw: 3482.79 Da

***I Theoretical pl: 6.75**

*I Expsy: SIB Bioinformatics Resource Portal

Separate the **isobaric diastereomeric impurity Gluc-(D)-His** and deamidated impurities (such as **Gluc-Glu 3**, **Gluc-Asp 28** and **Gluc-Glu 24**) from principal product **Gluc-(L)-His**

Complex surface structure in silica-based RP packings

C18 functional groups

C18 ligands are too bulky to totally react with free silanols present on the silica surface

Endcapping groups

Part of the remaining silanols can be "endcapped" with smaller silanizing agents

Free silanol groups

On a typical RP column, many silanol groups remain unreacted.

The chromatographic challenge of basic compounds

- The average pKa of free silanol groups is around 7.1, but their acidity could be enhanced by the presence of metal impurities

B-H⁺ protonated base

Ionisation cannot be entirely suppressed

Mixed mechanism process of hydrophobic interaction and ion-exchange with the silanols

First attempt: IP-RPLC

Eluent A: Water+0.1%TFA
Eluent B:ACN +0.1% TFA
T_{col}= 50 °C
UPLC Waters
UV@ 214 nm

	Column	Rs 1-2	Rs 2-3	Rs 3-4	Rs 4-5	μ _s (mm/s)	t ₀ = 60 minutes
1	ACQUITY UPLC® CSH C18 (100 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 μm 130Å	0.94	0.98	3.79	1.96	1.57	from 23% B to 28% B
2	ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1 mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 μm 300Å	-	-	2.28	1.57	1.40	from 24% B to 29% B
3	ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (100 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 μm 130 Å	-	-	1.20	0.80	1.58	from 23% B to 28% B
4	Halo peptide C18 (150 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.) 2.0 μm 160Å	0.87	0.92	2.56	1.84	1.67	from 25% B to 23% B
5	Ascentis peptide C18 (150 mm x 4.6 mm L. x I.D.) 2.7 μm 160Å	-	-	-	-	1.70	from 26% B to 31% B

Unacceptable asymmetry factors and poor diastereoselectivity between **Gluc(L)-His** and **Gluc(D)-His**.

Best resolution values were obtained on the **ACQUITY UPLC® CSH C18 (100 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 μm 130Å** column

Is there an effective strategy to reduce peak tailing for basic analytes?

Charged surface hybrid (CSH) packing materials

“Electrostatic repulsive interactions combined with RPLC-like dispersive interactions (i.e., **ERRP**) lead to the reduction of peak tailing of protonated bases under acidic pHs and shorter analysis times”

F. Gritti, G. Guiochon, J. Chromatogr. A, (2014) 1374,112-121.

“static”-ERRP

- Is it possible to generate the same molecular interactions, observed on CSH columns, on C18 columns only with a suitable mobile phase?

- **Yes**, by using a hydrophobic positively charged **ion pair agent** that gets adsorbed on the hydrophobic stationary phase (C18) generating a **positively dynamically charged surface**

“dynamic”-ERRP for peptide and small molecules

d-ERRP: How does it work?

The IP agent, present in mobile phase, gets adsorbed into the non-polar stationary phase due to its lipophilic alkyl chains. As a result, the **IP agent generates a positively dynamically charged surface**, decreasing the retention and reducing the peak tailing of protonated bases.

[Acid operating pH (~ 2.5)]

d-ERRP

Mitigate the influence of unwanted interactions, enhancing electrostatic repulsive interactions and hydrophobic interactions

d-ERRP: The importance of counterion

H₃PO₄

Highest resolution
between **Gluc-(L)-His** and **Gluc-(D)-His**
Highest peak tailing

Eluent A: Water+ H₃PO₄ 15 mM+ TBAOH 10 mM (0.258% w/v)_{app}pH 2.3
 Eluent B: ACN + H₃PO₄ 15 mM +TBAOH 10 mM (0.258 % w/v)_{app}pH 4.2
 T_{col}= 50 °C
 UPLC Waters
 UV@ 214 nm

CF₃COOH

Lowest resolution
between **Gluc-(L)-His** and **Gluc-(D)-His**
Lowest peak tailing

Eluent A: Water+ TFA 14 mM + TBAOH 10 mM (0.258% w/v)_{app}pH 2.6
 Eluent B: ACN + TFA 14 mM +TBAOH 10 mM (0.258 % w/v)_{app}pH 4.5
 T_{col}= 50 °C
 UPLC Waters
 UV@ 214 nm

d-ERRP : the importance of the concentration of additives in mobile phase

Loss in resolution between **Gluc-Glu 3** and **Gluc-Asp 28**

Column: ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 µm 300 Å
 UPLC Waters
 UV@ 214 nm

d-ERRP: High resolution analysis

ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1 mm L. x I.D.)
1.7 µm 300Å

$t_G=60$ minutes

	?	1	2	3	4	?	5
Area (%)	0.5	96.5	0.8	0.4	0.7	0.4	0.6
S/N	28	7558	63	41	69	35	59

Eluent A: Water+ TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 2.3
Eluent B: ACN + TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 4.2
 $T_{col}=50$ °C
UPLC Waters
UV@ 214 nm

Halo peptide C18 (150 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.)
2.0 µm 160Å

$t_G=60$ minutes

	?	1	2	3	4	?	5
Area (%)	0.4	97.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.6
S/N	32	5150	38	30	44	39	49

Eluent A: Water+ TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 2.3
Eluent B: ACN + TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 4.2
 $T_{col}=50$ °C
UPLC Waters
UV@ 214 nm

d-ERRP: high speed for high throughput analysis

ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1 mm L. x I.D.)
1.7 µm 300Å

$t_G=15$ minutes

Column	Rs 1-2	Rs 2-3	Rs 3-4	Rs 4-5	μ_r (mm/s)	$t_G=15$ minutes
ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1 mm L. x I.D.) 1.7 µm 300Å	1.79	1.89	4.21	5.41	1.40	from 22% B to 25% B

Eluent A: Water+ TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 2.3
Eluent B: ACN + TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 4.2
 $T_{col}=50$ °C
UPLC Waters
UV@ 214 nm

Halo peptide C18 (150 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.)
2.0 µm 160Å

$t_G=15$ minutes

Column	Rs 1-2	Rs 2-3	Rs 3-4	Rs 4-5	μ_r (mm/s)	$t_G=15$ minutes
Halo peptide C18 (150 mm x 3.0 mm L. x I.D.) 2.0 µm 160Å	1.89	1.96	3.91	6.43	1.67	from 22% B to 25% B

Eluent A: Water+ TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 2.3
Eluent B: ACN + TBAHSO₄ 10 mM _{app}pH 4.2
 $T_{col}=50$ °C
UPLC Waters
UV@ 214 nm

"static"-ERRP

Eluent A: Water+0.1%TFA
Eluent B:ACN +0.1% TFA

	Column	Rs 1-2	Rs 2-3	Rs 3-4	Rs 4-5	μ_r (mm/s)	$t_p = 60$ minutes
1	ACQUITY UPLC® CSH C18 (100 mm x 3.0 mm L. x 1.0 μ m) 1.7 μ m 300Å	0.94	0.98	3.79	1.96	1.57	from 23% B to 28% B

d-ERRP

Eluent A: Water+ TBAHSO₄ 10 mM pH 2.3
Eluent B: ACN + TBAHSO₄ 10 mM appH 4.2

	Column	Rs 1-2	Rs 2-3	Rs 3-4	Rs 4-5	μ_r (mm/s)	$t_p = 60$ minutes
1	ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (150 mm x 2.1 mm L. x 1.0 μ m) 1.7 μ m 300Å	2.52	2.10	4.64	7.80	1.40	from 18% B to 23% B
2	Halo peptide C18 (150 mm x 3.0 mm L. x 1.0 μ m) 2.0 μ m 160Å	2.24	2.09	3.87	7.70	1.67	from 18% B to 23% B

- An effective and sensitive method was developed for separation of **Gluc-(L)-His** and **Gluc-(D)-His**.
- The d-ERRP method is useful in the chromatographic analysis of basic compounds (both peptides and small molecules), reducing the peak tailing, decreasing the analysis time or decreasing the amount of organic modifier.

Cannabis sativa L.-Drug type

(-)- Δ^9 -trans-THC: ee > 99.7 %

Extreme chromatography

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SAPIENZA
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IMaSS
Italian Mass Spectrometry
Society

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Gabriella Pinto (Università di Napoli Federico II)

LC-MRM/MS quantification of protein hormones involved in female fertility

LC-MRM/MS quantification of protein hormones involved in female fertility

Gabriella Pinto^{1,3}, Anna Illiano^{1,2}, Amelia Mallardo¹, Stefania Serpico¹,
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4. *Istituto Diagnostico Varelli S.r.l., Via Cornelia dei Gracchi, 65, 80126 Napoli NA*
5. *Global Clinical Development, Merck Serono S.p.A, Rome, Italy, an affiliate of Merck KGaA*

Around 17.5% of the worldwide adult population (roughly 50% are women) is affected by infertility in their lifetime according to a recent estimate by of World Health Organization, displaying an increasing request for high-quality fertility care.

Routine monitoring of fertility hormones (proteins or steroids) is needed for diagnostic purposes to check the functionality of the reproductive system, to predict possible causes of infertility, and to monitor the response of pharmacological stimulation in medically assisted procreation techniques.

The dosage of fertility hormones in serum samples is a common clinical practice, but for some proteins, their absolute quantification is a great challenge due to biological variability and low serum concentrations [1]. For instance, since 1990, immunological assays like ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) are implemented in clinical labs for the measurement of serum AMH (anti-Müllerian hormone) by trying to increase the test reproducibility attributed to interference due to the binding of other serum proteins.

During the last few years, our research group is focusing on the development of liquid chromatography (LC) methods coupled with mass spectrometry (MS) for the quantification of multi-residue analysis for the simultaneous target proteins in single LC-MS/MS runs (2, 3). The multiplexed detection of selected proteins exploits the combination of the chromatographic separation and the filtering performances of triple-quadrupole analyzers capable to select precursor and fragment ions of specific m/z values.

In the present work, an LC-MS/MS method in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) ion mode has been developed to propose a molecular assay for the quantification of main protein hormones involved in fertility, *e.g.* AMH, LH (luteinizing hormone), FSH (follicle-stimulating hormone), TSH (thyroid-stimulating hormone), adiponectin, ghrelin, leptin, glucagon, obestatin.

The cohort of women sera ranging between 18 and 60 years was provided by an accredited analysis laboratory where ELISA assays were parallelly performed to validate the mass spectrometry method.

The analytical method of the internal standard by using isotope-labeled peptides was used for the quantitative determination of AMH. The present study was performed in collaboration with the Merck group warmly interested to set up a new method in alternative to the ELISA assay due to the dosage troubles in terms of reproducibility between the various laboratory kits.

The highly selective approach based on LC-MRM/MS aimed to propose an alternative valid to ELISA tests to quantify in a single run a wide panel of protein hormones crucial to get a more complete understanding of the reproductive health status or to support the progress of pharmacological stimulation in protocols of medically assisted fertilization.

- [1] Li H. W. R., Robertson D. M., Burns C. Ledger W. L. **2021**. Front Endocrinol 12:691432.
- [2] Illiano A., Melchiorre C., Cioci C., Pinto G., Di Rella F., Conforti A., Carbone L., Amoresano A. **2022**. Andrology Vol.11 Iss.S1 No:100002.
- [3] Illiano A., Pinto G., Gaglione R., Arciello A., Amoresano A. **2021**. Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom 35:e9166.

Extreme Chromatography Workshop (IMaSS sponsored event)

Italian Mass Spectrometry Society

LC-MRM/MS quantification of protein hormones involved in female fertility

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1

Infertility

WHO * supported the clinical definition for infertility as “a disease of the reproductive system defined by the failure to achieve a clinical pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse.”

Around 17.5% of the worldwide adult population (roughly 50% are women) is affected by infertility in their lifetime.

4 April 2023 | News release
1 in 6 people globally affected by infertility: WHO

* International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (11th ed.; ICD-11; World Health Organization, 2019).

Infertility diagnosis techniques

Diagnosis of Infertility

Hormonal dosage

Proteins

LH, FSH, AMH

Metabolites

Progesteron, Prolactin, Estradiol

Immunoassay (ELISA assays)

Imaging investigations

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Proteomics in clinical field

2. Choice of MS approach

Peptide

LC-ESI

1. Reduction in time of processing sample

Classical digestion protocol for 16-18 h

Global/Discovery proteomics

Qualitative	Quantitative
500-2000 identified proteins	Poorly reproducible, approx. quantitation

Targeted proteomics

Qualitative	Quantitative
10-100 candidate proteins	Precise reproducible, absolute quantitation

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Purpose

❖ Development and validation of a multi-residue method, based on tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) ion mode, coupled to liquid chromatography (LC) to monitor protein hormones

Gonadotropins

LH (luteinizing hormone)

FSH (follicle-stimulating hormone)

Ghrelin

Glucagon

Obestatin

TSHB (Thyroid stimulating hormone)

AMH (anti-Müllerian hormone)⁽¹⁾

Adipokines

Adiponectin

Leptin

Li H. W. R., Robertson D. M., Burns C. Ledger W. L. Challenges in Measuring AMH in the Clinical Setting. 2021. Front Endocrinol 24;12:691432

Experimental strategy

Serum samples (80) were provided by an accredited analysis laboratory (Varelli)

by ELISA assay (from Varelli laboratory)

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Reduction of digestion time

From 16/18 h to 2 h

Proteomics sample prep: S-Trap[®]

Less than 5 minutes | 1 hour | 16h

Multi-residue analysis

AMH
FSH
TSH
LH
Adiponectin
Leptin
Glucogone
Ghrelin
Obestatin

Multi-residue analysis

LC-MS/MS analysis in MRM ion mode

nanoBSM-Xevo TQ-XS Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry

Time	%A	%B	Flow (μL/min)	Injection Volume μL
0	93	7	3	2
5	93	7	3	2
40	50	50	3	2
42	5	95	3	2
45	93	7	3	2

BEH C18 peptide separation device (130Å, 1.7 μm, 150 μm X 50 mm) at 45°C

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How to set a MRM method?

- Selection of target proteins
- Selection of prototypic peptide for each protein and transitions

Find the aminoacidic sequence of the protein

Protein	Sequence	Precursor ion (m/z) Q1	Product ion (m/z) Q3	CE (eV)
AMH	GSGALTLQP R	556.8 (2+)	1055.6+	20
			968.6+	20
			911.6+	20
			798.5+	20
			727.4+	20
			614.4+	20

Creation of the MRM method

Selection of the best peptide and transitions

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Step for targeted approach

Selection of target proteins

Selection of prototypic peptide for each protein and transitions

LC-MRM/MS analysis and improvement of conditions

Data processing and interpretation

Data visualization

Statistical analysis
T-test student by
Perseus

REPORT

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Multi-residue LC-MRM/MS method

Proteins	Peptides	Transitions
Adiponectin	1	6
Leptin	3	18
Glucagon	4	22
Ghrelin	3	18
Obestatin	2	14
AMH	3	16
FSHB	3	16
TSHB	2	12
LHB	3	14
TOT	24	136

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Instrumental Response: AMH

❖ The internal standard method was performed by using the heavy peptide, isotopically labeled with $^{13}\text{C}_6$; $^{15}\text{N}_4$

AMH results: internal standard method

❖ Serum pools spiked with the **HEAVY PEPTIDE** were analyzed in triplicate by LC-MRM/MS method to realize the calibration curves.

LOD (fmol/μL)	LOQ (fmol/μL)	m	q	Linearity range (fmol/μL)	R ²	CV%	Recovery %
10.86±1.1	32.9±3.0	66118	248565	32.91-500	0.99	<15%	24.8%

MRM VS ELISA

Age range	LC/MS-MS (MRM) (ng/mL)	ELISA (ng/mL)
18-25	3.10	2.50
26-30	1.15	2.50
31-35	0.97	0.99
35-40	0.54	0.60
41-45	0.41	0.50
45->50	0.25	0.25

Same trend

CV%
<15 %

- High biological variability
- Different principle underlying the detection of the ELISA assay and MRM/MS method.

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Gonadotropins: relative quantification

- ❖ In women of reproductive age, LH and FSH levels fluctuate throughout the menstrual cycle¹ and stimulates follicular growth and ovulation²

- (1) R. Daniel et al. Serum gonadotropin and steroid patterns during the normal menstrual cycle 1971 Am J Obstet Gynecol . 111(1):60-5
- (2) J. Gottumukkala et al. Luteinizing hormone and follicle stimulating hormone synergy: A review of role in controlled ovarian hyper-stimulation. 2013 J Hum Reprod Sci. 6(4): 227-234

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Fertility hormones: relative quantification

M. Mitchell, et al., *Adipokines: implications for female fertility and obesity*. 2005. *Reproduction* 130(5):583-97

M.T. Sempere Ghrelin as a pleiotropic modulator of gonadal function and reproduction. Pgs 666-674. 2008, *Nat Clin Pract Endocrinol Metab* 4(12):666-74

M. Baig et al., Serum Leptin and Reproductive Hormones in Unexplained Infertile and Fertile Females. 2019 *Cureus*. 11(12): e6524.

Statistical analysis: heat map

The color intensity was associated with the log₂ value of peptide peak area.

Clustering between the data obtained below and above the threshold of 30 year old.

Perseus software

Good significance

Conclusions

Multi-residue method based on single runs LC-MRM/MS of hormone proteins

Absolute quantification of all monitored proteins

Next steps: matching ELISA assays data with MRM/MS ones and building up new normality ranges.

By enlarging the cohort of samples

Versatile methodology: MRM/MS method implementation by adding any proteotypic peptide from other proteins

Submitted draft
Work in progress

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ELISA VS MRM

ELISA Assays

Specificity based on antigen-antibody interaction

Very sensitive

Immunoassay

False positives

LC-MS/MS in MRM mode

Molecular Analysis based on peptides/molecular fragmentation

High specificity, selectivity and reproducibility

Multiplexed analysis: reduced time

Low throughput

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Stefano Brizzolara, Andrea Raffaelli (SSSup S. Anna, Pisa)
Challenges in the HPLC Separation and MS Detection of Carotenoids and
Liposoluble Vitamins

Challenges in the HPLC Separation and MS Detection of Carotenoids and Liposoluble Vitamins

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The study of secondary metabolites of plant species is an important issue for the comprehension of their growing pathways, but also very important for the classification of nutritional components present in the fresh products, as well as in their derivatives.

Most of these secondary metabolites possess strong antioxidant properties, useful for the protection of the plant itself in its environment, but very important also for their effect on free radicals in humans consuming vegetables in their diet. Several classes of antioxidant molecules are present: polyphenols, anthocyanins, carotenoids, hydro- and lipo-soluble vitamins and so on.

Most of these components can be investigated using “classic” C18 reverse-phase chromatography, as for instance polyphenols and anthocyanins, but other components, such as carotenoids and liposoluble vitamins, are quite more challenging, due to their very low polarity. The presence of relatively long carbon chains, indeed, cause a strong interaction with the C18 chains present onto the stationary phases. Several approaches can be used to improve the HPLC performances for these molecules. For example, one can lower these interactions using a C8 or a C4 column. On the other hand, it is possible to increase the eluting power of the mobile phase, working at high percentage of organic solvents or by addition of solvents with strong eluting power.

Another challenge deals with the ionization of these analytes: the extremely widely used ElectroSpray Ionization (ESI) is suitable only for polar compounds, and it is quite possible that the performance with so apolar compounds is relatively poor. We tested also Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization (APCI), that is effective also for low polarity compounds.

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RESEARCH CENTER

Challenges in the **HPLC Separation** and MS Detection of Carotenoids and Liposoluble Vitamins

Stefano Brizzolara, Andrea Raffaelli

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RESEARCH CENTER
Sant'Anna
Scuola Universitaria Superiore Pisa

Agricultural Commodities

PRE-Harvest

Agricultural Field

Harvest

POST-Harvest

Storage

Why Nutraceuticals are so important?

Image by Getty Images

Liposoluble Vitamins

Vit. A

- Vision
- Reproduction
- Bone health
- Immune system
 - Skin

Vit. D

- Strengthens bones
 - Heart health
- Minerals adsorption
- Immune system

Vit. E

- Balances hormones
- Immune system
- Flushes toxins

Vit. K

- Blood clotting
- Bone health
- Heart health

Chromatographic Challenges for Liposoluble Vitamins and Carotenoids

What about a C18 column?

Vitamin A

- retinol

Vitamin D precursors

- campesterol
- ergosterol
- stigmasterol

Vitamin E

- α -tocopherol
- β -tocopherol
- γ -tocopherol
- Δ -tocopherol

Vitamin K

- phyloquinone

Carotenoids

- lycopene
- β -carotene (pro-vitamin A)

What about a C18 column?

These C18 were available in the lab

We tried several times...BUT:

- weak peak separation
- weak and large peak
- only with 95% organic solvent
- some molecules never appeared

What does Literature report?

Most used stationary phases:

- C8
- ~~C18~~
- C30

And what if we use a C8 column?

A: Acetonitrile 0.1% Formic acid
B: H₂O 0.1% Formic acid

And what if we use a C8 column?

Again...???

- weak separation
- weak and large peak
- only with 95% organic solvent
- some molecules never appeared (Vit.A and Vit.D precursors)

XIC from Probe Column C8 Substanz Sample 21 - 100 µg, -1892 (5 fractions) Delta Toppaper (803.0 / 137.1), Gaussian smoothed (2.0 points)

Ok, OK.... I got it!
Let's try C30 column, it must work!!!

Most used stationary phases:

- ~~C8~~
- ~~C18~~
- C30

Ok, OK.... I got it!
Let's try C30 column, it must work!!!

A: Acetonitrile 0.1% Formic acid
B: H₂O 0.1% Formic acid

Ok, OK.... I got it!
Let's try C30 column, it must work!!!

Let's change LC gradient and modulate solvent polarity!

Increasing iso-propanol (20%)

A: Acetonitrile 0.1% Formic acid
B: H₂O 0.1% Formic acid

Increasing iso-propanol (30%)

Increasing iso-propanol (50%)

Increasing iso-propanol (50%)

Wait!

Let's stop at 30% isopropanol!

- Acceptable separation
- Acceptable peak shape

iso-propanol (30%)

HOWEVER:

- Retinol?
- Lycopene?
- β -carotene?

Next chromatographic step....?

Suggestions are welcome!!

Challenges in the HPLC Separation and **MS Detection** of Carotenoids and Liposoluble Vitamins

Stefano Brizzolara, Andrea Raffaelli

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Ionization Challenges for Liposoluble Vitamins and Carotenoids

Very Polar Compounds

- Ionization is not an issue for very polar compounds. Electrospray (ESI) is able to afford the desired ion.
- Very basic moieties in the analyte are prone to accept a proton to form $[M+H]^+$ ions.
- Acidic properties strongly assist the formation of $[M-H]^-$ species.
- Often, these analytes are intrinsically charged (salts).
- Response factor is, on average, quite strong.

Ionization Challenges for Liposoluble Vitamins and Carotenoids

Unpolar Compounds

- Unpolar compounds, such as liposoluble vitamins and carotenoids, further to the problems related to their chromatographic separation, may encounter some difficulty in their ionization.
- Some of these molecules look inappropriate for soft ionization techniques.

- ESI could not be the right choice in these cases, Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization (APCI) could help better.

ESI and the Selected Analytes

- The 11 selected analytes object of our investigation, ergosterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, α -, β -, γ - and δ -tocopherols, phylloquinone, retinol, β -carotene and lycopene were investigated by ESI in order to get the optimal parameters for the best sensitivity.
- Such an investigation is normally carried out by infusion with a syringe pump, so that the high flow rates required for APCI are difficult to use.
- In case of a following use of APCI for the analysis, this should not be a problem: it is universal accepted that an ion "do not remember" its ionization process.
- But in some instances, we can have a surprise...
- In this case, as we will see later, a "double" surprise.

ESI and Carotenoids

- Under ESI conditions both β -carotene and lycopene afford the radical molecular ion, $M^{\bullet+}$ in place of the expected protonated ion, $[M+H]^+$.
- Probably the molecular is not basic enough to catch a proton.
- On the other hand, positive ion ESI operates in oxidizing conditions, so that an electron can be ejected.

APCI and Carotenoids

- Under APCI conditions, there are strong protonating agents in the gas phase, capable to protonate even low polarity compounds, such as β -carotene and lycopene.
- Again, isomeric carotenoids give up to the same m/z value
- Some radical ion forms as well, but in this case the protonated form strongly prevails.
- How about MS-MS?

ESI and APCI Product Ions Spectra of β -Carotene and Lycopene (Identical)

How about the Other Analytes?

How about the Other Analytes: the Second Surprise...

Compound	ESI Prevalent Ion	APCI Prevalent Ion
Ergosterol	[M+H] ⁺	[M+H] ⁺
Campesterol	[M+H] ⁺	[M+H] ⁺
Stigmasterol	[M+H] ⁺	[M+H] ⁺
δ-Tocopherol	[M+H] ⁺	M ^{•+}
γ-Tocopherol	[M+H] ⁺	M ^{•+}
β-Tocopherol	[M+H] ⁺	M ^{•+}
α-Tocopherol	[M+H] ⁺	M ^{•+} and [M+H] ⁺
Phylloquinone	[M+H] ⁺	[M+H] ⁺
Retinol	[M-H ₂ O+H] ⁺	[M-H ₂ O+H] ⁺
β-Carotene	M ^{•+}	[M+H] ⁺
Lycopene	M ^{•+}	[M+H] ⁺

Two surprised face icons are present. One is next to the Tocopherol rows, with red arrows pointing to the M^{•+} ions. The other is next to the Retinol row, with a red arrow pointing to the [M-H₂O+H]⁺ ion.

One More Issue: Response Factor

Conclusions

- Besides the challenging search of the best chromatographic separation conditions, sterols, liposoluble vitamins and carotenoids induce a pain in the neck as far as their ionization.
- ESI is very efficient for polar molecules, less effective for low polarity ones.
- If no basic sites are present onto the molecule, ESI can produce the "classic" radical ion, $M^{\bullet+}$, thanks to the oxidation conditions.
- β -Carotene and lycopene, having no basic sites, indeed afford the radical ion under ESI conditions, whereas are able to form the protonated ion under APCI conditions.
- Strangely, tocopherols form the protonated molecular ion under ESI conditions, but tend to afford the radical molecular ion in APCI.
- In all cases, APCI offer a higher response factor, and hence a better sensitivity, in APCI than in ESI.

Thank you for your attention

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Andrea Armirotti (IIT, Genova)

A tricky challenge: LC-MS analysis of neurotransmitters and other polar metabolites
in mouse cerebrospinal fluid

LC-MS/MS QUANTIFICATION OF TWELVE NEUROTRANSMITTERS IN MOUSE CEREBROSPINAL FLUID

María Encarnación Blanco Arana^{1,3}, Olga Barca Mayo², Tiziano Bandiera^{1,3},
Davide De Pietri Tonelli² and Andrea Armirotti^{1,4,*}

1. *Graphene Labs, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia*
2. *Neuro miRNA Lab, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia*
3. *D3-Pharmachemistry, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia*
4. *Analytical Chemistry Facility, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia*

Background

So far, analytical investigation of neurotransmitters in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of rodent models has been limited to rats, given the intrinsic anatomic difficulties related to mice sampling and the corresponding tiny amounts of CSF obtained. This poses a challenge for the research in neuroscience, where many, if not most, animal models for neuronal disorders rely on mice.

New Method

We introduce a new, sensitive, fast and robust LC-MS/MS method to quantify a panel of twelve neurotransmitters (NT) from mouse CSF. The paper describes the sampling procedure that allows the collection of 1-2 microliters of pure CSF from individual mouse specimens.

Results

To test its applicability, we challenged our method on the field, by sampling 37 individual animals, thus demonstrating its strength and reliability.

Comparison with Existing Method(s)

Compared to other methods, our procedure does not involve any extraction nor derivatization steps: samples are simply diluted and analyzed as such by LC-MS/MS, using a dedicated ion pairing agent in the chromatographic setup. The panel of neurotransmitters that is quantified in a single run is also significantly higher compared to other methods.

Conclusions

Given the number of mouse models used in the neuroscience research, we believe that our work will pave new ways to more advanced research in this field.

LC-MS/MS QUANTIFICATION OF NEUROTRANSMITTERS IN MICE CSF: AN ANALYTICAL CHALLENGE

Andrea Armirotti, Ph.D.
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
(work done by Sion Blanco, now @OWL, Bilbao)

The role of neurotransmitters (NT) in signal propagation through nerves.....

Each neuron has
connections
with up to 15000
other neurons

Most NT are small, very polar compounds....

Difficult to handle from the reversed phase chromatographic standpoint (very low LogP)

Taken from compoundchem

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- NT are involved in all aspects of neurosciences (behavior, pain, emotions, organs control....anything)

- Most animal models in neurosciences are MICE models
- Most CSF NT data is from RAT models

CHALLENGE

Setup a sensitive, robust and high-throughput LC-MS/MS method to quantify NT in Mouse CSF

No derivatization

Easy sample preparation

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STEP 1: Sampling

Mice have tiny amounts of CSF

Need to be able to collect few microliters (1-3)

New and clean procedure, based on glass microcapillaries

- 10 minutes, from anaesthesia to sample
- Failure rate (blood contamination) <3%

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STEP 2: Chromatography

- No derivatization
- Zero or little retention in a set of standard RP phases
- No HILIC

→ ion pairing LC

HFBA

NFPA

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- Nice retention & peak shape
- Fast LC runs
- Good sensitivity
- High-throughput

Zero sample preparation:
Dilute 1ul + 9ul 0.1% FA with 200nM IS & inject

Eluents, column and conditions:

- A= 0.1% FA + 2.5 mM NFPA
- B= ACN
- 0-50% B in 5 min, flow 0.5ml/min.
- ACE Excel 2 C18-AR (150x2.1 mm)

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STEP 3: Detection & quantification

- Triple quad (Waters TQMS), MRM mode

Type of NM	Analyte	Abb.	Molecular formula	MW	LogP*	Rt	MRM Transitions	CV (V)	CE (eV)
AANM	Aspartate	Asp	C4H7NO4	133.1	-3.89	1.06	134 > 88 134 > 74	10 10	10 10
	Serine	Ser	C3H7NO3	105.1	-3.07	1.13	106 > 88 106 > 60	15 15	10 10
	Glycine	Gly	C2H5NO2	75.1	-3.21	1.21	76 > 30 76 > 48	15 15	5 5
	Glutamate	Glu	C5H9NO4	147.1	-3.69	1.28	148 > 84 148 > 130	15 15	15 10
	Glutamate-2,3,3,4,4-d5	Glu-d5	C5H4D5NO4	152.1	-	1.28	153 > 99	20	20
	γ-Aminobutyric acid	GABA	C4H9NO2	103.1	-3.17	2.34	104 > 69 104 > 87	20 20	15 10
γ-Aminobutyric acid-2,2,3,3,4,4-d6	GABA-d6	C4H3D6NO2	109.1	-	2.34	110 > 93	20	10	
MANM	Norepinephrine	NE	C8H11NO3	169.2	-1.24	2.61	152 > 107 152 > 135	25 25	15 10
	Epinephrine	EP	C9H13NO3	183.2	-1.37	2.87	166 > 107 166 > 135	30 30	20 15
	Dopamine	DA	C8H11NO2	153.2	-0.98	3.03	154 > 91 154 > 137	15 15	20 10
ACh	Acetylcholine	ACh	C7H16NO2	146.2	0.2	3.03	87 > 43 146 > 87	40 20	35 15
MANM	Serotonin	S H T	C10H12NO2	176.2	0.21	3.24	177 > 115 177 > 160	15 15	25 10
	Histamine	His	C5H9N3	111.1	-0.7	3.29	112 > 68 112 > 95	20 20	20 10
	Histamine-α,α,β,β-d4	His-d4	C5H5D4N3	115.1	-	3.33	116 > 99	20	15
	Methyl Histamine	MHis	C5H11N3	125.2	-0.6	3.29	126 > 68 126 > 109	20 20	15 5

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The choice of matrix for method setup & validation: artificial CSF

Commercial CSF:

Datasheet Citations (22) Reviews (1)

Biological Activity Technical Data Datasheets References

TOCRIS

Biological Activity for ACSF

Artificial cerebrospinal fluid (aCSF) is commonly used to maintain the oxygen supply, osmolarity and buffer pH of isolated neurons and brain slices in electrophysiology experiments. ACSF closely matches the electrolyte concentrations of cerebrospinal fluid and is prepared from high purity water and analytical grade reagents. Microfiltered and sterile. Final ion concentrations (in mM): Na⁺ 150; K⁺ 3.0; Ca²⁺ 1.4; Mg²⁺ 0.8; P 1.0; Cl⁻ 155.

Real CSF also carries glucose and proteins

We then used this aCSF*:

**150 mM Na⁺, 3 mM K⁺, 1.4 mM Ca⁺⁺, 0.8 mM Mg⁺⁺, 1 mM H₂PO₄⁻,
155 mM Cl⁻, 10 mM glucose, 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ BSA.**

* Korecka et al. J. Alz. Dis. 2014

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Method validation

	Quan. range LLOQ–ULOQ (μM)	Linearity (r ²)	Accuracy (% RE)						Precision (%RSD)					
			Intra-day			Inter-day			Intra-day			Inter-day		
			Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High
Asp	1-100	0.999	3.05	6.00	3.28	5.09	5.02	3.19	3.50	7.02	3.37	5.92	5.43	3.25
Ser	1-100	0.994	3.24	4.71	3.80	5.69	5.26	3.44	3.95	5.28	3.67	6.75	5.66	3.07
Gly	1-100	0.997	4.25	4.50	4.33	5.30	4.49	3.06	4.80	6.07	5.44	6.19	5.35	4.15
Glu	1-100	0.996	11.28	4.18	2.34	11.54	3.72	1.97	9.73	5.28	2.95	7.43	4.49	2.50
GABA	0.1-100	0.999	11.17	4.83	3.88	12.69	3.31	2.64	14.68	4.63	2.65	14.81	4.25	3.31
NE	0.1-100	0.992	12.02	4.28	3.99	12.35	2.99	2.86	14.84	4.93	3.44	14.41	4.21	3.48
EP	0.1-100	0.997	9.32	6.26	4.29	13.07	4.09	3.13	8.50	7.77	3.80	14.15	4.06	3.69
DA	0.1-100	0.999	13.01	3.36	4.07	13.20	4.52	3.60	10.83	4.59	2.87	14.95	5.61	3.39
ACh	0.1-100	0.999	11.53	5.63	6.33	11.93	7.94	4.22	12.41	7.05	3.31	11.83	6.90	4.35
5-HT	0.1-100	0.991	8.92	5.13	3.54	10.66	3.71	3.66	0.45	6.00	4.30	5.67	4.51	4.48
His	0.1-100	0.99	12.12	4.24	5.43	12.36	5.00	4.45	13.61	4.22	5.20	14.60	6.03	4.20
MHis	0.1-100	0.977	8.79	12.51	5.82	7.98	9.18	3.61	7.61	4.33	4.41	9.11	8.07	3.85

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Now we have the tool....let the fun begin!
 We produced NT data from a consistent N° of mice (around 100)
 NT dynamics in mice was not well described before....

- How are NT modulated by age?
- Differences males/females?
- Associations between different NT?
- Associations with other parameters?

The work is still ongoing...

- Heatmap analysis of NT levels (first 40 animals)

Rodan et al.
 Paediatric Neurology, 2015

Investigating the GABA/Glutamate ratio

- Very important in social behaviour
- Involved in autism disorder

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Investigating the ratio between excitatory (Glu/Asp) and inhibitory NT (GABA, Gly)

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Interactions of *graphene* based materials with the brain and the BBB

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Graphene based materials

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Graphene and neuronal system

Exposure to GO inhibits excitatory transmission and enhances inhibitory transmission

Bramini et al. ACS Nano 2016

A mechanism: altered Ca^{++} homeostasis linked with cholesterol metabolism

GO affects astrocytes functionality and alters neurotransmission

Chiacchiaretta et al. Nano Letters 2018

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Luckily, translocation of GO and FLG through the BBB is a rare event (NM are uptaken by the endothelial cells, but not translocated)

Castagnola et al. Nano Letters 2023

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**We can also track & quantify NT
in mice aqueous humor**

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Sion Blanco (former)

**Nara Liessi
Sine Bertozzi
Giuliana Ottonello
Dinu Ciobanu
Walter Mandaliti**

**Olga Barca Mayo (former)
Davide De Pietri Tonelli**

IMaSS
Italian Mass Spectrometry
Society

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The NFPA Legacy.... **263.5 m/z** in ESI-

Extensive ($10^5/10^6$ ion counts) and persistent contamination
Situation improved after:

- **Trashing column**
- **Repeated O/N washes with (water/ACN/MeOH/IPA 25% all)**
- **Extensive cleaning of ion source and ion optics**

Problem (almost) disappeared after 2 months of use (other projects)

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Luciano Callipo (Agilent)

2D-LC for Organic Molecules Identification in Wine Samples

2D-LC for Organic Molecules Identification in Wine Samples

Luciano CALLIPO, *Liquid Phase Separation Product Specialist, Agilent Technologies*

Nicola CIMINO, *Mass Spectrometry Product Specialist, Agilent Technologies*

The presentation shows the powerful of Agilent 1290 2D-LC as extreme chromatography technique. An application on red wine samples demonstrates that Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution can easily resolve complex mixtures by reversed-phase/reversed-phase, two-dimensional chromatography. The method was developed by means of a multi standard mixture and subsequently applied to detect polyphenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine in a qualitative and quantitative manner.

Further another application related to the coupling of an Agilent 1290 2D-LC Solution to an Agilent Accurate-Mass Quadrupole Time-of-Flight resulted to be a reliable solution for the measurement of polyphenolic compounds. The compounds separated by comprehensive 2D-LC approach were detected by the mass spectrometer and their accurate mass is measured. The compounds were identified by the LC Image LC \times LC-HRMS software package. Their mass was measured with high accuracy for the determination of their molecular formula.

References

1. D. Li and O. J. Schmitz “Use of Shift Gradient in the Second Dimension to Improve the Separation Space in Comprehensive Two-dimensional Liquid Chromatography”, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 405, 6511-6517 (2013).
2. Naegele, E., Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution, Agilent Technologies Application Note, publication number 5991-0426EN, 2012.
3. Naegele, E., Separation of Polyphenols by Comprehensive 2D-LC and Molecular Formula Determination by Coupling to Accurate Mass Measurement, Agilent Technologies Application Note, publication number 5991-0426EN, 2014.

2D-LC for Organic Molecules Identification in Wine Samples

Luciano Callipo
 Agilent Technologies Italia
 Liquid Phase Separation Product Specialist
 luciano_callipo@agilent.com

1 2/21/2019 DE29541885

Agilent 1290 Infinity II 2D-LC solution

Bringing the separation power of two-dimensional LC (2D-LC) to every user. Introduced since 2012.

<p>Are you sure?</p>	<p>Lack of the full picture?</p>	<p>In need for speed?</p>
	<p>Peak capacity per 30 min</p> <p>HPLC UHPLC 2D-LC</p>	<p>2D-LC</p> <p>Manual workflow</p> <p>Time</p>
<p>Avoid surprises and use full orthogonality to prove purity of compounds.</p>	<p>Resolve more compounds in highly complex samples.</p>	<p>Substitute manual prefraction or sample desalting with online methods.</p>

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What is a 2D-LC System?

2D-LC Instrument Setup

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Fundamentals of 2D-LC

The 2D-LC valve is the heart of every 2D-LC instrument

Full symmetry of both flow paths

The 2D-LC valve is a 2nd dimension fixed loop injector!

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Fundamentals of 2D-LC

Multiple Heart Cutting

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Fundamentals of 2D-LC

One System – 3 Techniques

Full Hardware Setup

(Multiple) Heart-Cutting 2D-LC (MHC 2D-LC)

Comprehensive 2D-LC (LCxLC)

High Resolution Sampling 2D-LC (HiRes 2D-LC)

There's no easier way to perform 2D-LC

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2D-LC Software Solutions

2D-LC Software for Highest Ease-of-Use and Performance

Choose your 2D-LC mode

Smart peak perking, peak-based parking, ASM and diverter valve

Click cuts for 2D analysis

2D gradient visualization

2D-LC Software Solutions

One Window to analyze your data

Screen your 1D separation...

Compare and report your results

...and see results of you 2D separation

Get quantitative 2D results

Use spectral data for compound identification

2D-LC Software Solutions

Setup shifted gradient

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2D-LC Software Solutions

Analyze your LCxLC data with GC Image LCxLC Edition

available from

Available Packages

UV and SQ Data
UV, SQ,(Q)TOF and QQQ Data

Our partner solution from GC Image offers sophisticated visualization and data analysis for **comprehensive 2D-LC** measurements

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Fruit Juices and Wine Analysis

Polyphenolic compounds are secondary plant metabolites including, for example, phenolic acids, flavonoids, coumarins and others. Many of these are present in grapes, berries, hop and herbs, as well as in food and beverages such as fruit juices, beer, and wine. This class of compounds has an antioxidative effect and potency to protect against free radicals.

The polyphenolic compounds occur in complex matrixes and their analysis requires a high separation capability. Therefore, two-dimensional liquid chromatography is the method of choice.

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Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution

Columns

- First dimension: Agilent ZORBAX RRHD Eclipse Plus C18, 150 × 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm
- Second dimension: Agilent ZORBAX RRHD Eclipse Plus Phenyl Hexyl, 50 × 3.0 mm, 1.8 μm

Thermostatted column compartment

First dimension column at left side at 25 °C. Second dimension column at right side at 60 °C. Two 80 μL loops are connected to the 2-position/4-port duo valve and are located at the left side. The valve is switched automatically after each second dimension modulation cycle

Autosampler

Injection volume: 5 μL. Sample temperature: 8 °C. Needle wash: 6 s in methanol

Diode array detector

Wavelength: 260/4 nm. Slit: 4 nm. Data rate: 80 Hz. Flow cell: 60 mm Max-Light flow cell

HPLC Method:

First dimension pump

Solvent A: Water + 0.1% formic acid. Solvent B: Acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid
Flow rate: 0.1 mL/min,
Gradient: 5% B at 0 min 95% B at 30 min 95% B at 40 min.
Stop time: 40 min. Post time: 15 min.

Second dimension pump

Solvent A: Water + 0.1% formic acid. Solvent B: Methanol + 0.1% formic acid.
Flow rate: 3 mL/min
Initial gradient: 5% B at 0 min, 15% B at 0.5 min 5% B at 0.51 min 5% B at 0.65 min
Gradient modulation: 0 min 5% B to 30 min 50% B, 0.5 min 15% B to 30 min 95% B, 0.51 min 5% to 30 min 50% B, 0.65 min 5% B to 30 min 50% B.

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-0426EN)

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Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution

Compound	Compound name	Compound	Compound name
1	Gallic acid	14	Morin
2	Esculin	15	Resveratrol
3	3,4 HO benzoic acid	16	Salicylic acid
4	HO Phenacetic acid	17	Luteolin
5	6,7 HO coumarin	18	Quercetin
6	HO Benzoic acid	19	Kaempferol
7	Syringic acid	20	Apigenin
8	Rutin	21	Naringenin
9	Naringin	22	Hesperetin
10	Coumaric acid	23	7 HO Flavone
11	Hesperidin	24	Pinosylvin
12	Ferulic acid	25	Chrysin
13	Myricetin	26	Flavone

A 50ug/ml Mix Std Solutions was used to optimized the method. To cover the largest possible space of the two-dimensional separation a large variety of compounds was used such as: phenolic compounds, glycosidic compounds and flavonoidics compounds

Red Wine samples were filtered through a syringe filter (0.45um) directly into a vial and injected

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(Publication 5991-0426EN)

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Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution

Three-dimensional display of the separation of the 26-compound standard mixture. The first dimension separation takes 40 minutes, and each second dimension separation takes 39 seconds.

Compound	Compound name	Compound	Compound name
1	Gallic acid	14	Morin
2	Esculin	15	Resveratrol
3	3,4 HO benzoic acid	16	Salicylic acid
4	HO Phenacetic acid	17	Luteolin
5	6,7 HO coumarin	18	Quercetin
6	HO Benzoic acid	19	Kaempferol
7	Syringic acid	20	Apigenin
8	Rutin	21	Naringenin
9	Naringin	22	Hesperetin
10	Coumaric acid	23	7 HO Flavone
11	Hesperidin	24	Pinosylvin
12	Ferulic acid	25	Chrysin
13	Myricetin	26	Flavone

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-0426EN)

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Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution

2D-LC analysis of red wine visualized with LCXLC software. The upper picture shows the compounds separated from the red wine sample in a 2-dimensional map including the UV spectrum of resveratrol. The lower part shows a 3-dimensional plot of the separation.

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-0426EN)

15

2/21/2019

DE29541885

Agilent

Qualitative and quantitative determination of phenolic antioxidant compounds in red wine and fruit juice with the Agilent 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution

Calibration of 1290 Infinity 2D-LC Solution for resveratrol quantification, 1–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ found in merlot: 4.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 4.5 mg/L.

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-0426EN)

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2/21/2019

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QTOF Mass Spectrometer for second dimension

- Simultaneous Hi Resolution, Extended Dynamic Range (10GHz)
- Higher resolution (>60k @2722m/z, >30k @118m/z)
- DIA Quadrupole-resolved All-Ions (Q-RAI)
- Capillary gate valve
- High sensitivity, Isotopic fidelity, Robustness
- 50 Hz Data Acquisition Speed.

17

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Tune Mix – Measured data

18

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Separation of Polyphenols by Comprehensive 2D-LC and Molecular Formula Determination by Coupling to Accurate Mass Measurement

Instrument parameters

Columns	
1 st dimension	Agilent ZORBAX RRHD Eclipse Plus C18, 2.1 × 150 mm, 1.8 μm (p/n 959759-902)
2 nd dimension	Agilent ZORBAX RRHD Eclipse Plus Phenyl-Hexyl, 3.0 × 50 mm, 1.8 μm. (p/n 959757-312)
Method	
1 st Dimension pump	
Solvent A	Water + 0.1 % formic acid
Solvent B	Acetonitrile + 0.1 % formic acid
Flow rate	0.1 mL/min
Gradient	0 minutes 5 % B – 30 minutes 95 % B, 40 minutes – 95 % B
Stop time	40 minutes
Post time	15 minutes
2 nd Dimension pump	
Solvent A	Water + 0.1 % formic acid
Solvent B	Methanol + 0.1 % formic acid
Flow rate	3 mL/min
Initial gradient	0 minutes - 5 % B, 0.4 minutes - 15 % B, 0.41 minutes - 5 % B, 0.5 minutes - 5 % B
Gradient modulation	0 minutes 5 % B to 30 minutes 50 % B, 0.4 minutes 15 % B to 30 minutes 95 % B, 0.41 minutes 5 % B to 30 minutes 50 % B, 0.5 minutes 5 % B to 30 minutes 50 % B

TCC	
1 st dimension column	On the left side at 25 °C
2 nd dimension column	On the right side at 60 °C
Two 80-μL loops are connected to the 2-position/4-port-duo valve and are located on the left side.	
The valve is switched automatically after each 2 nd dimension modulation cycle. In this case, the loops are used in a co-current manner (the loops are filled and eluted from the same sides).	
Autosampler	
Injection volume	5 μL
Sample temperature	8 °C
Needle wash	6 seconds in methanol
MS-TOF or Q-TOF in TOF mode	
Drying gas flow	9 L/min
Drying gas temperature	300 °C
Sheath gas temperature	400 °C
Sheath gas flow	12 L/min
Nebulizer pressure	45 psi
Capillary voltage	3,500 V
Nozzle voltage	300 V
Fragmentor voltage	175 V
Mass range	100–1,000 m/z
Data rate	10 Hz

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-4733EN)

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Separation of Polyphenols by Comprehensive 2D-LC and Molecular Formula Determination by Coupling to Accurate Mass Measurement

Figure 1. Separation of a mixture of 22 polyphenolic compounds by comprehensive 2D-LC and molecular formula determination by coupling to accurate mass measurement by time-of-flight MS.

Table 1. Polyphenolic standard compounds separated by comprehensive 2D-LC and determined by accurate time-of-flight mass measurement.

No.	Compound	Formula	MW	[M-H] ⁻	RT I (min)	RT II (sec)	m/z	ppm
1	Galic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	178.0215	169.0142	3.53	2.51	169.0142	0.28
2	3,4-Hydroxyl benzoic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	154.0266	153.0193	6.53	10.73	153.0195	1.10
3	Esculin	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	340.0794	339.0722	7.53	17.79	339.0714	2.23
4	Hydroxyl benzoic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	138.0317	137.0244	8.53	15.56	137.0245	0.60
5	5,7-Hydroxyl coumarin	C ₉ H ₆ O ₃	178.0366	177.0193	9.53	20.49	177.0197	2.08
6	Butin	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₆	210.0634	209.0461	12.03	14.50	209.0467	0.97
7	Coumaric acid	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	164.0473	163.0401	12.03	11.69	163.0399	1.63
8	Ferulic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	254.0579	253.0506	13.03	14.01	253.0511	2.42
9	Naringin	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₄	580.1792	579.1719	13.53	17.78	579.1726	1.16
10	Hesperidin	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₄	610.1898	609.1825	13.53	18.84	609.1822	0.48
11	Salicylic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	138.0317	137.0244	15.53	15.30	137.0243	0.86
12	Morin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	302.0427	301.0354	16.03	16.14	301.0360	2.07
13	Resveratrol	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	228.0786	227.0714	16.03	13.43	227.0711	1.18
14	Luteolin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.0477	285.0405	17.03	19.23	285.0404	0.22
15	Quercetin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	302.0427	301.0354	17.03	17.59	301.0358	1.41
16	Apigenin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	270.0528	269.0455	18.03	21.26	269.0450	2.03
17	Naringenin	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₅	272.0685	271.0612	19.03	19.52	271.0607	1.83
18	7-Hydroxyl flavone	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	238.0630	237.0557	19.53	22.42	237.0559	0.77
19	Kaempferol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	286.0477	285.0405	19.53	19.04	285.0412	2.59
20	Hesperetin	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₆	302.0790	301.0718	20.03	20.67	301.0720	0.79
21	Pinosylvin	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃	212.0837	211.0765	22.03	19.71	211.0768	1.64
22	Chrysin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	254.0579	253.0506	23.53	22.42	253.0511	1.85

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Separation of Polyphenols by Comprehensive 2D-LC and Molecular Formula Determination by Coupling to Accurate Mass Measurement

Figure 2. Accurate profile mass spectra from comprehensive 2D-LC coupled to time-of-flight mass measurement. Compounds: (1) Gallic acid, $C_6H_5O_7$ [M-H]⁻ calc.: 169.0142, [M-H]⁻ measure.: 169.0142, mass accuracy: 0.29 ppm, (10) Hesperidin, $C_{28}H_{34}O_{15}$ [M-H]⁻ calc.: 609.1825, [M-H]⁻ measure.: 609.1822, mass accuracy: 0.40 ppm, (13) Resveratrol, $C_{14}H_{12}O_5$ [M-H]⁻ calc.: 227.0714, [M-H]⁻ measure.: 227.0711, mass accuracy: 1.18 ppm, (21) Fisetin, $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ [M-H]⁻ calc.: 211.0705, [M-H]⁻ measure.: 211.0708, mass accuracy: 1.64 ppm.

Agilent Application Note
(Publication 5991-4733EN)

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Michela Antonelli (IRBM)

Practical Considerations for Peptide Analysis

Practical Considerations for Peptide Analysis

Michela ANTONELLI

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Peptides represent a growing class of therapeutics due to their target specificity, lower toxicity, and higher potency. Although LC-MS remains the gold standard for peptide quantification, due to the benefits of multiplexing, improved specificity, broader linear dynamic range, and faster method development times, is not without its challenges.

Their large and complex structure makes the development of sensitive and robust peptide analytical methods often more time consuming due to the variety of challenges encountered with these molecules. In fact, these challenges start with peptide handling and are carried through to sample extraction, chromatographic and MS method development. One of the most analytically and less predictable challenge is maintaining solubility throughout sample preparation and analysis and non-specific binding. Peptides tend to bind to many surfaces (vials, plates, LC tubing, column stationary phases, injectors, etc.) in a concentration dependent, yet non-linear manner. A systematic investigation of peak performance and distortion is extremely useful to elucidate non-specific interactions between peptides and stationary phases.

Because of their size, charge state distribution and complex MS/MS fragmentation, sensitivity by mass spectrometry may be lower than typical small molecules, often necessitating greater LC and sample preparation method development. To gain better sensitivity and selectivity sample concentration and improved sample extraction techniques beyond basic protein precipitation are often required.

Special emphasis will be placed on addressing peptide chromatographic challenges and providing several key recommendations that can significantly increase the specificity, sensitivity, and reliability of MS detection for both linear and cyclic peptides.

Practical considerations for peptides analysis

Michela Antonelli, PhD
Rome, 8th May 2023

Analytical method development for peptides

Issues for the analysis

- Sample extraction
- Analytical column screening
- Separation column capacities
- Adsorption to solid surfaces
- Recovery and Matrix Effect

Aim of the analysis

- Good peak area and intensity
- Optimum symmetry factor
- Absence of tailing and fronting
- High chromatographic recovery
- Satisfying separation column capacity

Linear and Cyclic Peptides in drug discovery

Characterized by:

- 500 Da < MW < 5000 Da
- Target specificity
- Low toxicity
- High potency

- Desmopressina
- Octreotide
- Ciclosporina A

Sample Extraction

- Efficiency of the extraction solvent

Screening of the best extraction solvent

- Peptide characteristics:
Cyclic peptide with disulfide bond
~ 5000 Da

- Analytical condition:
Waters Peptide BEH C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm
Column T: 50°C Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min
Mobile Phase : A: H₂O + 0.1% Formic acid
B: ACN + 0.1% Formic acid

Time (min)	% B
0.00	2
0.20	2
2.50	80
2.60	95
3.50	95
3.60	2
4.50	2

→ Best extraction was obtained with ACN

Screening of the best extraction solvent

→ Extraction with MeOH and EtOH containing 1% TFA showed good response for both analytes. EtOH negatively impacted the peak shape → MeOH was selected as the best extraction solvent

	Dimer			Monomer		
	AVG peak area	SD	Recovery %	AVG peak area	SD	Recovery %
Spike Before	2988	228	74	33658	2408	82
Spike After	4049	62		41206	1486	

Extraction recovery with MeOH +1%TFA was evaluated by spiking medium before and after extraction with a 3 µM mixture of both dimer and monomer (two replicates)

Screening of the best extraction solvent

- The calculation of the chromatographic parameters for the dimeric and monomeric peptide showed peak distortion when using EtOH as extraction solvent, although with a good peak response.

Monomer

Ext. solvent	Rt	Area	Tf	As	Width 50%
MeOH_1% TFA	2.34	1.03E+04	1.16	1.27	0.019
EtOH_1% TFA	2.33	9.53E+03	0.62	0.24	0.024
ACN_1% TFA	2.34	3.06E+03	0.94	1.07	0.028
Acetone_1% TFA	2.34	3.29E+03	0.96	1.06	0.020

$$\text{Equations: } A_s = b/a$$

$$T_f = a + b/2a$$

Dimer

Ext. solvent	Rt	Area	Tf	As	Width 50%
MeOH_1% TFA	2.69	3.23E+03	1.04	1.01	0.016
EtOH_1% TFA	2.69	1.44E+03	0.89	0.78	0.015
ACN_1% TFA	2.69	9.31E+02	1.18	1.73	0.028
Acetone_1% TFA	2.69	7.26E+02	0.81	0.55	0.048

Screening of the best extraction solvent

8 volumes of MeOH 1%TFA (extraction solvent) were used for the extraction of both analytes from the medium.

Extraction recovery was evaluated by spiking cell medium before and after extraction with a 3 μM mixture of both dimer and monomer (two replicates):

- ✓ 8 volumes of MeOH+1% TFA to 1 volume of medium
- ✓ Vortex, centrifuge 15 min at 13000 rpm
- ✓ Direct injection into LC-MS

	Dimer			Monomer		
	AVG peak area	SD	Recovery %	AVG peak area	SD	Recovery %
Spike Before	2445	269	100	23408	1386	89
Spike After	2448	57		26411	757	

→ Recovery was increased by using 8 volumes of MeOH + 1% TFA instead of 4 volumes

Column screening

- Choice of the best stationary phase
- Chromatographic condition parameter evaluation

Column screening: Case study n°1

Peptide characteristics:

- Symmetrical peptide
- 10 AAs
- ~ 1300 Da

XSelect peptide CSH (Waters), 2.1 x 100 mm

Triart BIO C18 (YMC), 2.1 x 100 mm

Fortis BIO C18 (Fortis), 2.1 x 100 mm

Luna Omega C18 (Phenomenex), 2.1 x 100 mm

Kinetex 1.7 μM XB-C18 (Phenomenex), 2.1 x 100 mm

Accucore-150-C18 (Thermo), 2.1 x 100 mm

Column screening: Case study n°2

Several columns tested to achieve good separation between dimer and monomer:

Waters XSelect CSH C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm

Waters BEH Pep C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm

Waters Peptide CSH C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 100 mm

Waters BEH C8, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 100 mm

Waters BEH C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 100 mm

Dimer

Monomer

Column	Component Name	Area	Rt	Tf	As
BEH Peptide	Monomer	2.10E+07	2.58	1.61	1.99
	Dimer	1.30E+05	2.6	1.77	2.52
CSH Peptide	Monomer	1.50E+07	2.84	1.2	1.35
	Dimer	4.80E+04	2.97	4.1	5.03
BEH C8	Monomer	9.60E+06	3.42	2.31	3.28
	Dimer	5.50E+04	3.47	1.49	1.74

Column	Component Name	Area	Rt	Tf	As
BEH C18	Monomer	1.60E+07	2.33	1.33	1.68
	Dimer	2.40E+06	2.67	1.08	1.1
Xselect CSH C18	Monomer	5.70E+06	2.58	1.38	1.69
	Dimer	1.40E+04	2.76	1.26	1.41

→ Best separation was obtained with a BEH C18, 130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 100 mm

Final LC-HRMS condition

- LC conditions
 - ✓ Column: Waters BEH C18, 2.5 µm, 130 Å, 2.1x100 mm
 - ✓ Column T: 70 °C
 - ✓ Flow rate: 0.6 mL/min
 - ✓ Mobile phase A: H₂O + 0.02% TFA + 0.08 FA%
 - ✓ Mobile phase B: MeCN + 0.02% TFA + 0.08 FA% + 10% Isopropanol
 - ✓ Inj vol: 10 µL
- LC Gradient

- HRMS conditions
 - ✓ Instrument: Triple TOF 6600+ (Sciex)

Time (min)	% B
0.00	20
3.50	50
3.51	90
6.30	90
6.31	20
10.00	20

Extracted ion Chromatogram

Dimer
Retention time: 2.67 min
Capacity factor: $k' = 2.9$ (Ref. >2)
Tailing factor: 1.05 (Ref. <1.5–2.0)

Monomer
Retention time: 2.34 min
Capacity factor: $k' = 2.5$ (Ref. >2)
Tailing factor: 0.94 (Ref. <1.5–2.0)

Cyclic peptide: separation column capacities

Mixture of cyclic peptides:

- ~ 12-14 AAs
- ~ 2000 Da
- Differentiation for one amino acid

Analytical condition:

Waters Peptide CSH C18, 130 Å, 2.5 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm

Column T: 60°C Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Mobile Phase : A: H₂O + 0.1% Formic acid

B: ACN + 0.1% Formic acid

Time (min)	% B
0.00	1
0.25	1
4.00	50
4.75	95
5.50	95
5.51	1
6.00	1

Matrix effect

- Peak intensity
- Peak shape

Quantitation of an endogenous peptide in Monkey plasma

Development and qualification of a liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) based method for the quantitation of a peptide in monkey plasma.

Isoforms could interfere with quantitation of the bioactive peptide.

Potential issues reported in the literature:

- Met oxidation
- Aggregation
- Adsorption to surface

Matrix effect in Monkey plasma

- Cyno plasma (reduced, alkylated, precipitated with 4%TCA and extracted with SPE) was injected.
- 500 ng/mL of B-CAM-IS in solvent (70/30/0.1 ACN/H₂O/FA + 1mM DTT) was continuously infused.

Matrix effect: post-column infusion

XIC Pep-End

Peak area
1211 cps

Peak area
2920 cps

Peak area
994 cps

XIC Pep-IS

Gradient 1

Gradient 2

Gradient 3

Waters BEH, 1.7 μ m – 2.1 x 50 mm
A: H₂O + 0.1% FA
B: ACN/H₂O/IPA 95/5/0.5 + 0.1% FA
0.7 mL/min

Time	%A	%B
0	99	1
3.00	70	30
3.50	10	90
4.50	10	90
4.60	99	1
7.00	99	1

Time	%A	%B
0	99	1
4.00	70	30
4.50	10	90
5.00	10	90
5.10	99	1
7.00	99	1

Time	%A	%B
0	99	1
2.00	70	30
2.50	10	90
3.10	10	90
3.20	99	1
7.00	99	1

Quantitation in Monkey plasma

Several columns tested: CSH Peptide, Xselect, BEH C8, Atlantis Premiere (Waters), Advance BioPeptide Plus (Agilent) → poor peak shape or low chromatographic recovery

Final conditions

Column: Waters BEH, 1.7 μ m – 2.1 x 50 mm

A: H₂O + 0.1% FA

B: ACN/H₂O/isopropanol 95/5/0.5 + 0.1% FA

Sample composition: H₂O/ACN 70/30 + 0.1% FA

Inj vol: 10 μ L

Gradient:

Time	%A	%B
0	99	1
3.00	70	30
3.50	10	90
4.50	10	90
4.60	99	1
7.00	99	1

Parameter	Value
Peak vol	55 \pm 3.2 μ L
Peak width	4.7 \pm 0.3 sec
K*	3.29
N	17000
Tailing factor	1.4

Analysis of Dimeric peptide in Human serum

Development and qualification of a liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) based method for the analysis of dimeric peptide in human serum.

Potential issues:

- Matrix effect
- Decrease of peak intensity
- Distortion of peak shape

Matrix Effect: Dimeric peptide in human serum

• Analytical condition:

Waters Peptide CSH C18, 130 Å,
2.5 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm
Column T: 50°C
Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min
Mobile Phase :
A: H₂O + 0.1% Formic acid
B: ACN + 0.1% Formic acid

1. LC gradient:

Time (min)	% B
0.00	2
1.00	2
5.50	60
5.60	95
8.00	95
8.10	2
11.0	2

2. LC gradient:

Time (min)	% B
0.00	2
1.00	2
10.0	60
11.0	95
14.0	95
14.1	2
17.0	2

Conclusions:

- Peptide chromatographic optimization represents the turning point to increase the specificity, sensitivity, and reliability of MS detection for both linear and cyclic peptide.
- Best quantitation results can be achieved only after a fine tuning of all the settings and the critical evaluation of both LC and MS parameters.

May 8th

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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Luigi Mondello (Università di Messina)

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry
for the Analysis of Complex Food Samples

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry for the Analysis of Complex Food Samples

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Food and food products are a fruitful source of bioactive molecules e.g. flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, etc. For their analysis, the most employed technique is liquid chromatography; however, sometimes the complexity of such samples exceeds the separation capability afforded by conventional LC. A valuable alternative is represented by comprehensive two-dimensional liquid chromatography (LC×LC), emerged three decades ago, and represents a powerful analytical method for the deep investigation of complex real-world samples. LC×LC involves the coupling of two or more orthogonal or quasi-orthogonal separation systems with different selectivity with the aim of detecting both major and minor bioactive components. The hyphenation to mass spectrometry, thanks to its improved identification capability, represents a third valuable dimension to the LC×LC technique.

The present contribution has the goal to illustrate the benefits of the LC×LC approaches used for separation of complex food and food-related samples. Integrated platforms, namely RP×RP and HILIC×RP, coupled to mass spectrometry, have been successfully investigated. With regards to RP×RP set-up a comparison of four different gradient elution strategies in the second dimension, e.g. full in fraction, segmented, parallel and shifted gradient programs is reported.

The developed set-ups are a valuable tool for the quali-quantitative study of food products, considering their great complexity and high dimensionality.

Acknowledgment: The authors are thankful to Shimadzu and Merck Life Science Corporations for the continuous support.

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry for the Analysis of Complex Food Samples

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IMaSS—Italian Mass Spectrometry Society

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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Rome
May 8, 2023
Marconi room
CNR Headquarters
Piazzale Aldo Moro, 7, Rome

Foods and food products analysis

- Food and food products contain several bioactive molecules with pharmacological activity e.g. flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, and so on.
- Despite many studies have been focused on the chemistry and bioactivity of these products, there is still much interest in the discovery of novel compounds from different sources.
- Analytical methods MUST be selective and sensitive enough to detect both major and minor components.
- A powerful alternative to conventional 1D-LC analysis is comprehensive two-dimensional LC (LC × LC).

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Liquid Chromatography (LC×LC)

1D-LC is often unable to provide the required separation power to resolve all the compounds

Insufficient resolution in 1D

Coelutions

Comprehensive Two-dimensional Liquid Chromatography (LC×LC) is a promising analytical tool since it combines **two different separation procedures** (dimensions) for the analysis of one sample, allowing the separation of the compounds present in the sample by **two different retention mechanisms**, greatly increasing peak capacity.

LC×LC: background

To be considered “comprehensive”, multidimensional separation must respect these rules:

1. Every part of the sample is subjected to two different separations.
2. Equal percentages (either 100% or lower) of all sample components pass through both columns and eventually reach the detector.
3. The separation (resolution) in the first dimension is essentially maintained.

P. Schoenmakers et al., LCGC Europe, 2003, 16, 335

Method Development in LC×LC

Selected combination can be chosen on the basis of analytes properties.

- ➡ NP×RP: a difficult combination (mobile phase immiscibility)
need for “peak focusing” adjustment
- ➡ RP×RP: need for orthogonality tuning (high correlation)
- ➡ HILIC×RP: need for “peak focusing” adjustment

RP vs. HILIC as 1st D of LC×LC for the elucidation of the polyphenolic content of food and natural products

- ➡ RP-LC ×RP-LC is the most frequently used LC×LC system to analyze the polyphenolic content of food and natural products
(huge number of small molecules with similar molecular weights, polarities, and structures).

HILIC vs RP

- ➡ HILIC separations have a great efficiency for the characterization of hydrophilic and polar compounds employing water and organic solvents as mobile phases.

Combination of HILIC and RP-LC in on-line mode:

highly miscible mobile phases

good orthogonality values, considerably increasing the number of separated compounds.

Strategies for improving RP×RP separations

1) “Full in fraction” (only one generic and steep mobile phase range in each repeated 2D run)

Advantages:

- Provides satisfactory separation for compounds with similar polarity.

2) “Segmented gradient” (at least two generic and steep mobile phase range in each repeated 2D run)

Advantages:

- Provides significant bandwidth suppression effects.
- The probability of “wrap-around” effects is reduced.

3) “Parallel gradient” (only one single 2D gradient)

Advantages:

- Longer 2D elution time (post-gradient equilibration is not necessary)
- It can be employed in highly correlated RP-LC×RP-LC systems.

4) “Shift gradient” (continuous change of the gradient)

Advantages:

- Reduces the likelihood of “wrap-around” phenomena.
- As for the “segmented gradient” the concentration of the organic solvent can be adjusted to suit the sample retention.

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Liquid Chromatography (LC×LC)

Instrumentation in LC×LC

Case study 1

POLYPHENOLS IN SUGARCANE
(Saccharum officinarum)

RP-LC × RP-LC/PDA-MS

RP-LC×RP-LC/PDA-MS Method

- **First dimension: RP-LC**

Column: Ascentis Cyano 250 x 1.0 mm i.d., 5 μm d_p

Mobile phase: A) 0.075% formic acid in water; B) 0.075% formic acid in ethanol (gradient mode)

Flow rate: 10.0 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$

Injection volume: 5 μL

- **Second dimension: RP-LC**

Column: Ascentis Express C18 , 30 x 4.6 mm i.d., 2.7 μm d_p

Mobile phase: A) 0.075% formic acid in water; B) 0.075% formic acid in methanol (gradient mode)

Flow rate: 4.0 mL/min

Loop size: 20 μL (2 position, 10 port valve)

Modulation time: 2.0 min

- **Detection: PDA, ESI-MS**

- **Samples:** sugarcane leaves

RP-LC×RP-LC Plot of Sugarcane

Approaches for Increasing separation space in RP-LC × RP-LC

Continuously Shifted

Segmented in Fraction

RP-LC × RP-LC Plot of Sugarcane

RP-LC × RP-LC Plot of Sugarcane

Evaluation of the system performance

1D	Column	250x1.0 mm, 5.0 μm		
	Gradient	172 min		
	n_C	30		
		FULL in FRACTION	CONTINUOUSLY SHIFTED	SEGMENTED in FRACTION
2D	Column	30x4.6 mm, 2.7 μm		
	Gradient	120 s		
	n_C	46	26	24
2D	Mod. time	2 min		
No. of 1D transferred fractions		86	86	86
Theoretical ^a $2Dn_C$		1380	780	720
Practical ^b $2Dn_C$		129	256	308

^a ${}^1n_C \times {}^2n_C$

^b corrected for under-sampling and orthogonality

Identified polyphenolic compounds identified in sugarcane

#	Total t _R (min)	UV (nm)	[M-H] ⁻	Molecular formula	Peak identification
1,2	56.2, 58.4	238/323	353	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	Caffeoylquinic acid isomers ?
3,4	72.7, 73.4	238/307	325	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₈	Coumaric acid glucoside ?
5, 6, 7	74.5, 74.6, 76.5	235/321	367	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₉	Feruloyl quinic acid isomer ?
9	106.4	267/307	335	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₈	Caffeoylshikimic acid
10	108.5	267/307	563	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₁₄	Schaftoside
11	112.6	267/307	563	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₁₄	Isoschaftoside
12	112.9	268/353	519	-	Tricin derivative
13	114.7	267/356	461	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	Diosmetin-8-C-glucoside
14	115.1	265/354	637	C ₂₉ H ₃₄ O ₁₆	Tricin-7-O-neohesperidoside
15	116.8	266/357	549	-	Luteolin derivative
16	118.6	268/349	447	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	Luteolin 7-glucoside
17	118.9	266/357	491	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₁₂	Tricin-7-O-glucoside
18	122.9	266/307	563	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₁₄	Apigenin derivative
19	130.9	266/307	563	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₁₄	Apigenin derivative
20	139.4	266/353	625	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₇	Quercetin-3-O-beta-D-glucopyranosyl
21	141.7	266/357	329	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇	Tricin
22	153.6	267/307	446	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₀	Swertisin (7-O-methylapigenin-6-C-gluc.)
23	163.4	266/307	431	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	Vitexin
24	165.7	266/356	651	C ₂₉ H ₃₂ O ₁₇	Tricin-7-O-rhamnosylgalacturonide

IT-TOF-ESI-MS (precursor ion: 367.1029)

Feruloyl quinic acid isomer

it is not possible to discriminate between the positional isomers!!!

IT-TOF-ESI-MS/MS (precursor ion: 367.1029)

Feruloyl-quinic Acid Isomers (FQA)

expansion of the 2D chromatogram
(254 nm UV plot)

Case study 2

METABOLITES IN
(*Brassica juncea* L.)

RP-LC × RP-LC/PDA-MS

Brassica juncea L.

- ✓ *Brassica juncea* L. is an amphiploid species, which belongs to Brassicaceae family.
- ✓ It is an oilseed crop very rich in iron, vitamin A, and vitamin C and also it contains potassium, calcium, riboflavin thiamine, and β -carotene.
- ✓ It has antiseptic, diuretic, emetic, and rubefacient properties.
- ✓ Due to numerous caffeoyl and sinapoyl derivatives (not commercially available) quantification is normally performed after acidic and/or alkaline hydrolysis*

A=Flavonols
B=Hydroxycinnamic acids

* Olsen et al., J. Agric. Food Chem. 2009, 57, 2816-2825

HPLC-PDA/MS of *Brassica juncea* leaf extract

Sample and sample preparation: *Brassica juncea* leaf extract (using a mixture of methanol:water (60:40, v/v)) was redissolved in 1 mL of the same extraction mixture of methanol:water (60:40, v/v).

Column: Ascentis Express C18, 150×4.6 mm; 2.7 mm;
Mobile phase: A: Water 0.15% CH₃COOH B: ACN;
Flow-rate: 1.0 mL/min; gradient elution;
Column oven: 30 °C; P= 250 bar. (Start with 5% B);
Inj. Vol. 10 μ L

RP-LC×RP-LC/PDA-MS Method

First dimension: RP-LC

Mobile phase:

- A) 0.15% acetic acid in water;
- B) acetonitrile

Elution: gradient mode

Flow rate: 10.0 μL/min

Injection volume: 2 μL

Second dimension: RP-LC

Mobile phase:

- A) 0.15% acetic acid in water;
- B) acetonitrile

Elution: gradient mode

Flow rate: 2 mL/min

Injection volume: 10 μL

Loop dimensions: 10 μL; Mod. time: 1 min.

RP-LC×RP-LC Plot of *Brassica juncea* L.

Multi (Three-step) Segmented gradient

Arena et al., Molecules 2020, 25, 1235

Repeatability of RP-LC×RP-LC Plots of *Brassica juncea* L.

Peak	Compound	Mean TtR	RSD (%) n=3	Mean Area	RSD (%) n=3
1	Malic acid	19.321	0.021	59664	0.784
2	Km-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside	34.541	0.018	159713	1.21
3	Sinapoyl-feruloyl-triglucose	42.729	0.008	95465	0.548
4	Disapoylgentiobiose	47.793	0.007	1481389	1.018

RP-LC (C18) vs. LC×LC analysis of metabolites *B. juncea* L.

RP-LC (C18) vs. LC×LC analysis of metabolites *B. juncea* L.

PDA vs. MS spectra of metabolites in *Brassica juncea* L.

Same UV-VIS spectra but different ESI-MS spectra

PDA vs. MS spectra of metabolites in *Brassica juncea* L.

Different UV-VIS spectra and different ESI-MS spectra

Semi-Quantitative Determination of the Flavonoid Content of *Brassica juncea* Cultivars

- ✓ Tentative identification was performed based on their PDA, MS, and literature data.
- ✓ Among the major classes of compounds identified, **organic acids, (acetylated) tri- and tetrasaccharides, and (acetylated) mono- and disaccharides**, were recognized.
- ✓ Due to the lack of commercial standards, quantification of **native** *Brassica* spp content was carried out by following an established approach in the field of food and natural product analysis.
- ✓ Three standards, as representatives of the distinct chemical classes, *i.e.*, **Km 3-O-glucoside, Isorhamnetin 3-O-glucoside, and Qn 3-O-glucopyranoside**, were chosen and calibration curves were prepared.

Calibration curve for Quercetin-3-O-glucopyranoside ($\lambda=330\text{ nm}$)

Polyphenol quantification by RP-LC×RP-LC-PDA

Quantitative results (mg/g) for quercetin derivatives by RP-LC and RP-LC×RP-LC-PDA

* Not separated from the rest of the matrix

** Coeluted in mono-dimensional analysis

1. Qn 3-caffeoylsophoroside-7-glucoside
2. Qn 3-sophoroside-7-glucoside
3. Qn 3-hydroxyferuloyl-sophoroside-7-glucoside
4. Qn 3-sinapoyltrigluconide-7-glucoside
5. Qn 3-digluconide

Case study 3

POLYPHENOLS IN *Rhus coriaria* L. (Sumac)

HILIC × RP-LC/PDA-ESI-MS

Rhus coriaria L. (Sumac)

- *Rhus coriaria* L. belong to the Anacardiaceae family which are native to Mediterranean area, eastern and western North America, sud Africa and Asia.
- The chemical composition and the biological properties of the plants depend from the countries of origin.
- Recently polyphenols such as gallic acid, **gallotannins**, anthocyanines, and pyrano-anthocyanines in sumac have been object of research.
- The fruits show antimicrobial, antioxidative, anthelmintic, anti-proliferative and antinflammatory activities.
- On the basis of literature data on the biological activities of different type of *Rhus*, and considering that few results are reported on the Sicilian type, the latter is worth of investigation *.

General structure of gallotannins

* S. Wang al., Food Chem. 2017, 237, 431-443

HILIC×RP-LC/PDA-MS Method

- Ascentis Express C18 (0.5 cm x 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
- Internal Volume: 50 μL (60 % Stationary)

Sample and sample preparation

- Six different samples:
- **Sumac I**: Sicilian fresh sumac harvested in May 2020
- **Dried Sumac I**: Sicilian fresh sumac harvested in May 2020 and sun dried
- **Sumac II**: Sicilian fresh sumac harvested belatedly in October 2020
- **Dried Sumac II**: Sicilian fresh sumac harvested belatedly in October 2020 and sun dried
- **Commercial sumac I**
- **Commercial sumac II**

≈15 g grinded fruit (with seeds) weighted

Water addition
(100 mL)

Stirring for 1 h at 40° C

Undervacuum filtration
(filter 0.45 μm)

Collection of the solution

Freezing and lyophilization

Lyophilized extract
(purple red ≈2 g)

HILIC×RPLC-PDA Plot of Sicilian Sumac

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids

ZIC-HILIC: zwitterionic functional groups (sulfobetaine), charge balance 1:1

83 compounds were positively identified

HILIC×RPLC-PDA Plot of Sicilian Sumac

Anthocyanins

ZIC-HILIC

HILIC×RPLC-PDA Plot of Commercial Sumac

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids

Performance evaluation of the HILIC×RPLC-PDA Set-up

	Sumac I	Dried sumac I	Sumac II	Dried sumac II	Commercial Sumac I	Commercial Sumac II
¹ D peak capacity, ¹ n _c	67	73	68	61	55	59
² D peak capacity, ² n _c	43	39	44	55	48	46
Theoretical peak capacity, ^{2D} n _c	2875	2829	2971	3381	2673	2691
Effective peak capacity, ^{2D} n _c ^{1,*}	1085	986	1114	1382	1181	1130
Orthogonality A ₀ **	0.79	0.82	0.90	0.84	0.79	0.72
Corrected peak capacity, ^{2D} n _{c,corr} ***	858	814	1004	1161	934	817

*Li X, Stoll DR, Carr PW. Equation for peak capacity estimation in two-dimensional liquid chromatography. Anal Chem. 2009 81, 845-850.

$${}^{2D}n_{c, \text{effective}} = \frac{{}^1n_c \times {}^2n_c}{\sqrt{1 + 3.35 \times \left(\frac{{}^2t_c - {}^1n_c}{{}^1t_p}\right)^2}}$$

** Camenzuli M, Schoenmakers, P.J. A new measure of orthogonality for multi-dimensional chromatography. Anal. Chim. Acta 2014 838, 93-101.

*** ${}^{2D}n_{c, \text{corrected}} = {}^{2D}n_{c, \text{practical}} \times A_0$

Quantitative results for chemical classes by HILIC×RPLC-PDA

Concluding Remarks

- Comprehensive liquid chromatography (LC×LC) can be a powerful separation tool in the field of food and natural product analysis, allowing to separate, identify and quantify compounds in a complex sample.
- Compared to one-dimensional LC the higher separation power of LC×LC allowed to reduce risk of co-elutions and matrix effects, allowing more reliable quantification.

Comparing the RP×RP and the HILIC×RP approaches

	RP×RP	HILIC×RP
Advantages	Solvent compatibility	Increased orthogonality and peak capacity
	Possibility of different RP stationary phases	Better structure organization of the 2D plots
Disadvantages	Low orthogonality and peak capacity	Solvent incompatibility
	Need of “gradient strategies”	Need of dedicated interfaces (AM)

- Both the approaches can be successfully used in the determination of the bioactive compounds in food matrices.

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- *Shimadzu Corporation*
- *Merck KGaA*
- *Thank you all for your attention*

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Emanuele Ceccon (Restek)

Polar analytes and large panels, is there necessarily a need to rely to extreme solutions? A reflection on going back to basic

Polar analytes and large panels, is there necessarily a need to rely to extreme solutions?

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Summary

- What does it mean to be a Polar analyte
- Which are the main interactions and why to use them
- Example of construction of a method
- Amino acids panel
- Quats panel
- Conclusions

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What does it mean be a polar analyte?

- **Una molecola è polare se :**
 - Se possiede dei legami polarizzati, si intende dei legami covalenti tra due atomi che hanno una differenza importante di elettronegatività, questo induce la creazione di cariche parziali (q) da una parte e dall'altra di questo legame
 - la posizione media di queste cariche parziali non deve essere confusa

* <https://www.cours.fr/richter.fr/lycee/premiere-s/1sppc-6-de-la-structure-a-la-polarite-dune-entite/>

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Raptor

What does it mean be a polar analyte?

- A bit of refresh about possible interactions and mechanism w can acually rely on
 - Rp stationary phases
 - Hilic phase
- Different mechanism do have diffrent ways to be tuned
- Buffers, acids , temperature , amount of organic are the main used modifiers

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Main interactions

Dispersion

Interazioni Dispersive

Interazioni di Van der Waals
Forze di Dispersione di London

« Spostamento » della densità elettronica creando un momento dipolare temporaneo tra le molecole non-polari nei dintorni

Interazione maggiore con i ligandi alkyl (ex: C18)

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Main interactions

POLARIZZABILITA' e Pi-Pi

Le molecole neutre non-polari sono generalmente dei costrutti elettronici simmetrici (sferici) nella loro nube elettronica. In presenza di un campo elettrico, questa nube elettronica può essere deformata. La facilità di questa deformazione è definita **polarizzabilità** di un atomo o di una molecola.

Questa distorsione creerà un momento dipolare temporaneo a livello della molecola, legata alla polarizzabilità della molecola.

Polarizability- π - π bonding between the electrons of the aromatic ring interact with the π - π electrons of the aromatic solute

Use for Aromatic Analytes

Pi-Pi Interaction

Polarizability

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H-Bonding.

- Interaction between an atom hydrogenated and one with negative charge (like nitrogen, oxygen or fluorine)

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Ion Exchange (anion)

Anion Exchange Activity - the exchange of negatively charged ions between solutes and silica/ligand

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Ion Exchange (cation)

FluoroPhenyl

Cation Exchange : the exchange of negatively charged ions between solutes and silica/ligand

F⁻

Usefull for basic compounds (pH < pKa) a/o polars

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Hilic

Hilic is a mode, like RP, in hilic we do rely to all interactions valid for RP

Hilic partitionig vs RP Partitioning

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Hilic Interaction and stationary phases

- HYDROPHILIC PARTITIONING/ADSORPTION
 - Hydrophilic Partitioning
 - Hydrogen bonding
- ION EXCHANGE
 - Anion, Cation exchange
 - Hydrogen Bonding

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Explanations about HILIC mechanism

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HILIC

What impact more partitioning

- Major impact on partitioning/adsorption is given by mobile phase and stationary phase selection
- Buffers may reduce electrostatic repulsion, ph help (bare silica PKA from 3.8-4.5)

- Hilic stationary phase:
 - Diol,Amide,Zwitterionic (High partitioning,low IEX)
 - Bare silica, Polar X (Partitioning and IEX, IEX for bare silica still lower than PFP)
 - PFP (high IEX low Partitioning)

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HILIC Equilibration time

Most important point

- Is usual to hear Hilic give rt not stable
- Not all "hilic" columns have same needs of equilibration time
- All of them need a longer equilibration time than RP columns

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Amino Acids analysis

Amino Acids Structures

Non-Polar Amino Acids

Positively Charged Amino Acids

Polar Amino Acids

Negatively Charged Amino Acids

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Amino Acids analysis

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Amino Acids in Human Plasma on Raptor Polar X

LC_07097

Peak	t _r (min)	Precursor Ion	Product Ion
1. Ethanolamine	1.06	62.0	44.1
2. Acetyltyrosine	1.83	224.1	138.1
3. γ-Aminobutyric acid	2.25	104.0	69.0
4. D-Aminoisobutyric acid	2.27	104.1	30.0
5. β-Alanine	2.32	90.0	35.1
6. Tryptophan	3.31	205.1	140.1
7. Leucine	3.40	132.1	86.1
8. Phenylalanine	3.53	166.1	120.1
9. Isoleucine	3.60	132.1	86.1
10. Alloisoleucine	3.77	132.1	86.1
11. Methionine	4.15	150.1	104.1
12. Valine	4.27	118.1	72.1
13. Tyrosine	4.27	182.1	138.1
14. Arginine	4.32	179.2	70.1
15. D-Aminobutyric acid	4.57	104.0	33.1
16. Piperacilic acid	4.60	130.0	84.1
17. 1-Methylhistidine	4.62	170.1	124.1
18. Taurine	4.65	126.1	108.1
19. Histidine	4.65	156.1	110.2
20. Anserine	4.67	241.2	109.1
21. Carnosine	4.67	227.2	110.1
22. 3-Methylhistidine	4.68	170.0	126.0

Peak	t _r (min)	Precursor Ion	Product Ion
23. Lysine	4.68	147.1	84.1
24. Ornithine	4.72	133.1	70.0
25. Hydroxylysine	4.84	163.1	138.1
26. Alanine	4.86	90.0	44.1
27. Proline	4.89	116.1	70.1
28. Sarcosine	5.03	90.0	44.1
29. Threonine	5.15	120.1	74.1
30. Glycine	5.19	76.1	30.1
31. Hydroxyproline	5.26	132.1	86.1
32. Adenosylhomocysteine	5.30	285.0	133.7
33. Glutamine	5.43	147.1	84.1
34. Homocitrulline	5.43	190.1	84.1
35. Serine	5.46	108.1	60.1
36. D-Aminopropionic acid	5.53	162.1	98.1
37. Asparagine	5.54	133.1	74.1
38. Citrulline	5.61	176.1	139.1
39. Homocysteine	6.20	269.1	136.0
40. Glutamic acid	6.26	149.1	84.1
41. Cystathionine	6.75	233.1	134.0
42. Cystine	6.99	241.1	132.0
43. Phosphoethanolamine	7.32	142.0	44.1
44. Argininosuccinic acid	7.41	201.1	70.1
45. Aspartic acid	8.00	134.1	74.1

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Paraquat and Diquat on Raptor HILIC-Si

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Chlormequat, Mepiquat, Paraquat, and Diquat on Raptor HILIC-Si by LC-MS/MS

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Method 1

method 2

Mobile Phase

A: Water, 50 mM ammonium formate, 0.5% formic acid
 B: Acetonitrile:water 90:10, 50 mM ammonium formate, 0.5% formic acid

Time (min)	Flow (mL/min)	%A	%B
0.00	0.6	0	100
4.00	0.6	25	75
7.00	0.6	25	75
7.01	0.6	0	100
10.00	0.6	0	100

Mobile Phase

A: Water, 50 mM ammonium formate, 0.5% formic acid
 B: 25:75 Water:acetonitrile, 50 mM ammonium formate, 0.5% formic acid

Time (min)	Flow (mL/min)	%A	%B
0.00	0.6	0	100
4.00	0.6	35	65
4.01	0.6	0	100
7.00	0.6	0	100

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A Good sequence to achieve a fast development

This is what i always follow

1. Look at you analytes LOG-P
(hydrophilic/hydrophobic,keep numbers for all analytes)
2. Find a common PKA zone for all your analytes
3. Look at the net just now, just now on you are really able to evaluate work done from other people
4. Define the mode (Hilic-RP-Direct phase)
5. Are present really similar analytes?
 - 1.Think to add different mechanisms along Partitioning/Dispersion
Look at the mechanisms you will like to put in place to understand if any additive, sample diluent , temperature is needed or if is enough to arrange a gradient

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Conclusions

- Too often be ause we do think to save ime w do no use our knowledge and use to rely to other people solution, without any idea if what writtene do have sense
- Often spend 20 30 minutes using your brain do save a lot of hours/day of wasted trials
- To know your analytes and reention mechanisms allow to save time just as long we think to them before start our work.
- Plus or less never put on a c18 and just play some runs lead to spend less time

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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Antonio Triolo (Menarini, Firenze)

LC-MS hints and tips: how to help an imperfect pair to live a perfect married life

LC-MS hints and tips: How to help an imperfect pair to live a perfect married life

Antonio TRIOLO

Menarini Ricerche Firenze

The direct interfacing of HPLC with MS (LC-MS) can be considered as one of the major technological breakthroughs of the past four decades, producing a cascade of scientific and technical achievements in many fields, such as Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences, Environment protection, Forensic investigations, Food safety, to name just a few. At the beginning of the '80s of the past century, the only affordable and consolidated interfacing of MS with a separation technique was GC-MS, whose applicability was obviously limited to volatile and thermostable analytes, and the coupling of HPLC with MS was considered as a sort of mirage, since the technical problems to directly transfer the analytes from a liquid flowing at around 1 mL per min, into an instrument working in the gas phase at 10^{-6} bar and less, looked almost insurmountable. The introduction of Electrospray and APCI in the early 90's was immediately perceived by the scientific community as a quantum leap respect to the previous pioneering LC-MS interfacing techniques, not only for the seamless accommodation of the common HPLC flow rates, but even more for the application to very labile molecules and for the dramatic extension of the observable molecular mass ranges, up to proteins and beyond, even with common, low-cost mass analyzers.

All this led to a sort of democratization of LC-MS: on one hand, simple, relatively low-cost and easy to use instruments were introduced in many laboratories, dramatically extending the possible applications at the advantage of non-MS specialized scientists and technicians; on the other hand, the commercial availability of affordable, highly automated and increasingly performing instrumentation has provided the whole scientific community with an essential tool for highly sophisticated investigations in a wide array of disciplines.

Since the early 90's, HPLC and MS evolved in parallel, in the sense that in most cases the progresses of one technique found immediate application into the other, and vice-versa. Thus, the introduction of new stationary phases, micro and nano HPLC, use of sub-2 μm particles and multidimensional HPLC was paralleled by the introduction of MS instruments with increasing resolving power and mass range, novel ion activation techniques, and orthogonal ion separation technologies based on ion mobility.

This presentation will give some practical pharmaceutical applications of the above concepts, in which, starting from some basic theoretical principles, typical analytical problems are solved, including LC-MS analysis of very polar compounds and use of non-MS compatible mobile phases.

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Menarini Global R&D

LC-MS hints and tips: how to help an imperfect pair to live a perfect married life

Antonio Triolo
Menarini Ricerche Spa

Workshop Extreme Chromatography, Roma May 8, 2023

...well, 1 mL/min of liquid H₂O would generate... 1230 m³/min inside the source????!

WOW!
but it's easy!
...and works great!
...and now I can see proteins with a quad!!!!

...but what about putting the source itself at P_{atm}???

...and they lived happily ever after

The gifts of HPLC ...

	Multi-dimensional HPLC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • separation of (very) complex mixtures
	Micro / nano HPLC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low-amount samples, increased sensitivity
	Polymeric & Hybrid stationary phases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • higher pH stability, different selectivity
	Core-shell technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • higher efficiency (via better packing density and faster mass transfer) • higher sensitivity (due to higher efficiency) • lower backpressure
	Monolithic columns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • super-low backpressure for high-speed analyses • direct injection of dirty / viscous samples
	Sub-2 µm particles: UHPLC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • higher efficiency and sensitivity, at the expense of higher backpressure and need of dedicated instrumentation • flexible choice between higher throughput and higher resolution
	Many diverse stationary phase chemistries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RP (C18, C8, C4, C6 Phenyl, PFP,) • HILIC • IEX and Mixed mode

3

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The gifts of MS...

	Ionization at P_{atm}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless accommodation of standard HPLC flow rates • «Gentle» treatment of labile molecules • Availability of different techniques (ESI, APCI, APPI...), to analyze a wide diversity of molecular classes
	High-Resolution MS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost on selectivity • Info on elemental composition
	Tandem MS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural information from unfragmented analytes • Complex mixtures • Golden standard for LC-MS quantitation (SRM mode)
	Ion activation alternatives to CID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECD, ETD, UVPD (Large Molecules) • EAD (Small and Large Molecules)
	Orthogonal techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ion mobility: separation by size, shape and charge state

4

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The outcome of LC and MS coupling ...

Democratization of LC-MS:

- Diffusion of simple, low-cost instruments in non-MS specialized laboratories
- Introduction of instruments for highly sophisticated discoveries in many disciplines
- Acquisition and processing ease of use

Mass Spectrometry should be for scientists, not only for mass spectrometrists
(F. W. McLafferty)

Environmental Studies

DNA, RNA

Food Science

OMICS!

Bioanalysis

Molecular assemblies

Protein structure and dynamics

5

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What HPLC can do for better LC-MS?

HOW MANY TIMES MUST I TELL YOU TO USE VOLATILE MODIFIERS IN MOBILE PHASES!

... AND TO SEND ME BETTER-RESOLVED PEAKS!! AND NARROW, NOT LIKE THAT SORT OF HILLS, YOU BLOCKHEAD!!!

BUT NOT TOO NARROW, I NEED TO SCAN ALL OF THEM!!!!

... AND HURRY UP! I DON'T WANT TO SPEND AN HOUR PER RUN BLOWING NITROGEN AND RUNNING SCANS FOR 2-3 MISERABLE PEAKS!

6

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How do I get better resolution?

Eluting conditions:
Mobile phase, temperature, pH

Stationary Phase:
Hydrophobicity, steric effect, H-bond, cation-exchanging capacity...
C18, C8, Phenyl, PFP, HILIC, mix-mode
Eluting Conditions:
Mobile phase, temperature, pH

Smaller particles
UHPLC
Smaller column ID
(optimum for LC-MS)

Improving R: choice of the stationary phase with best α

C18, 1.7 μ m, 50 x 2.1 mm

C18 AX 1.7 μ m 100 x 2.1 mm

Polar stationary phase, an early example (1998): ManNAc-NH₂

Column: Ultrasep ES Sacch

Peak number	Ret. time	[M+H] ⁺	Identity
1	4.42	222	2-N-acetylmannosamine
2	4.85	221	ManNAcNH ₂
3	5.31	220	ManNAcNH ₂ isomer
4-7	8.38-13.57	424	Di-Mannosylamine and isomers

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How do I get quicker analyses?

Wang Y et al. J.Chromatog. A. 2012;1228:99-109.
DOI: 10.1016/j.chroma.2011.08.085.
Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328206327>

$$N \propto 1/d_p$$

Use smaller particle size!

- ❖ No loss of efficiency at high flow rates with $d_p < 2 \mu\text{m}$
- ❖ Flexible choice between shorter run time and better resolution
- ❖ Two limits:
 - Backpressure
 - MS scanning rate

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How do I get more MS Sensitivity?

Use smaller particle size!

$$\frac{N_{1.7\mu m}}{N_{5\mu m}} \cong 3 \quad \Rightarrow \quad N \propto \frac{1}{w^2} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{w_{1.7\mu m}}{w_{5\mu m}} \cong \frac{1}{1.7} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{pk-h_{1.7\mu m}}{pk-h_{5\mu m}} \cong 1.7$$

- Sharper peaks means higher analyte concentration and enhanced sensitivity (ESI is concentration-sensitive!)

Use smaller column ID!

$$V_{col} = L \times \pi r^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{Vol\ 4.6}{Vol\ 2.1} \cong 5$$

- With equal amount injected, analyte concentration is inversely proportional to ID²: changing from 4.6 to 2.1 mm ID results in 5x higher sensitivity.

11

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Improvement of ESI MS response using 1.0 mm vs 2.1 mm ID columns

Drug, M1, M2 standards 5 ng/mL

$$\frac{Vol\ 2.1}{Vol\ 1.0} \cong 4.4$$

12

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What if I need to use non-MS compatible mobile phases?

2D LC-MS - A: chromatographic peak sampling

13

2D LC-MS - B: Peak desalting and elution

14

2D LC-MS analysis of Glibenclamide

- Time delay between UV and MS: about 1.6 min.
- Desalting-elution cycle : 1.6 min (including cartridge re-equilibration).

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Thanks for your attention!

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Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Anna Severoni (Thermo)

Ion-exchange chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (IC-MS)
for analysis of polar compounds

Ion-exchange chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (IC-MS) for analysis of polar compounds

Anna SEVERONI

Thermo

Traditionally, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) partnered with mass spectrometry (MS) is usual setup analytical laboratories. In recent years, we have seen an increase in number and nature of components and the need to couple other type of chromatography to MS. In particular, more polar compounds have been included in the list of analytes to be analysis by MS for this reason ion chromatography (IC) is now one of the chromatography techniques.

IC was used in the past as standalone technique for the inorganic ions, in the last decade the coupling with MS has emerged as effective analytical technique complementary (or alternative) to the LC-MS for separation of small polar species and ionic ones in different area of applications delivering stability, retention time reproducibility and sensitivity.

IC-MS is now an established technique in several research areas from environmental, food and forensic. Moreover, IC can be applied in pharmaceutical sciences, clinical chemistry, and metabolomics where it can open to future development and new applications to better analyses high polar components whose analysis is very difficult with C18 chromatography or HILIC or mix mode column. In this presentation we will see some examples of applications in various filed where IC can be used as an established and routine technique.

Ion-exchange chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (IC-MS) for analysis of polar compounds.

Dott.ssa Anna Severoni

Application Scientist, LSMS, Applied Markets & Pharma, Italy
Rome May 8, 2023

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1 Module - Basic considerations Orbitrap - Exploris - Oct. 2022

Positioning Modern LC-Techniques

Adapted from: H. Hayen, Nachrichten aus der Chemie, 58, April 2010

What is Ion (Exchange) Chromatography

Separation principles in chromatographic purification

Ion (Exchange) Chromatography

Ion Chromatography: Anion-Exchange Mechanism

Advantages of ion chromatography

- Direct method
 - ✓ – No chemical derivatization
- Excellent selectivity
- High sensitivity
 - ✓ – Low chemical noise
- Ideal for separations of polar ionic compounds
- Low cost
 - ✓ – No solvent needed
- Metal free

Ion Chromatography (IC) provides needed sensitivity and selectivity

IC-MS Setup

MS can be single quadrupole, triple quadrupole, or High Resolution – Accurate Mass (HRAM) hybrids (Thermo Scientific™ Orbitrap™, and Ion Trap)

Principles of RFIC - Eluent Generation

RFIC – Reagent-free IC without manual eluent preparation

Suppression Technology in IC Removes The High Chemical Background

Chemistry and Ion Movement Anion Suppression

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... in an Thermo Scientific™ Dionex™ ERS™ electrolytically regenerated suppressor

IC-MS Technology: Electrospray Ionization

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- IC-MS typically uses an electrospray (ES) source to ionize analyte molecules
- Produces molecular ion species (little or no fragmentation)
- Sensitive and Rugged
- Requires high mobile phase volatility
 - Requires elevated ESI Probe temperature
 - May require addition of organic modifier (acetonitrile or isopropanol) to aid more efficient desolvation
- Non-volatile salts may precipitate inside ESI capillary
 - Matrix diversion recommended for high ionic strength sample matrices
- Matrix ions can suppress ionization
 - Minimized by chromatographic resolution of analyte ions matrix ions

Applications Example

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Polar Ionic Pesticides in the News

- Widely used in agricultural production
- High frequency of residues of certain compounds detected in food
- EPRW 2014 – number of poster on residues of chlorate in leafy vegetables (and perchlorate residues from fertiliser use)
- 2016: Alliance for Natural Health USA: reported 10 of 24 breakfast foods had residues of glyphosate (86 – 1,327 µg/kg) (www.anh-usa.org)
- 2016: Glyphosate residues in German beers
- Glyphosate under scrutiny after the [International Agency for Research on Cancer \(IARC\)](#) that informs the World Health Organization (WHO) on cancer risk factors, [classified glyphosate as a 'probable carcinogen' last March 2015](#)
- Blog: Analysis of the Pesky Polar Pesticides: In the News, but What's the Answer?
<http://analytequru.com/analysis-of-the-pesky-polar-pesticides-in-the-news-but-whats-the-answer>

Polar Pesticides

Many different approaches to analyzing polar pesticides are in place

- Low *m/z* of molecular & fragments ions
- Non-specific MS/MS transition with low response – issues with ion ratios
- High concentration of co-extractives in QuPPE Extracts- limited clean-up
- Signal suppression
- System contamination
- Adequate chromatographic retention for compliance with EU SANTE criteria
- Repeatability of retention time
- Chelation of analytes with metals
- Low recoveries & need for Isotopically Labelled Internal Standards (ILIS)

Extracted Ion Chromatograms for Glyphosate at 10 ng/g in Wheat

- MRL for glyphosate (currently parent only) in wheat grain: = 5 mg/kg (China), 30 mg/kg (North America), 10 mg/kg (EU)
- Inclusion of metabolites of glyphosate the method and customer investment is future proofed should the EU Residue definition change

Conductivity Traces of Anions Present in Different Matrices

Validation Results

Component	Matrix	LOD [ng/L]	LOQ [ng/L]	REC [%]			RSD [%]		
				10 ng/L	20 ng/L	50 ng/L	10 ng/L	100 ng/L	1000 ng/L
Fosetyl	Drinking	2.5	5	133	122	132	9.0	1.3	0.7
	Bottled	1	2.5	121	123	128	2.0	0.9	1.1
	Surface	2.5	5	105	105	104	2.0	1.1	0.6
Glufosinate	Drinking	5	10	133	121	95	9.3	2.4	0.9
	Bottled	5	10	56	112	96	4.1	3.4	0.8
	Surface	5	10	124	111	93	2.2	1.6	1.2
AMPA	Drinking	5	10	91	93	83	9.1	2.3	0.8
	Bottled	5	10	109	107	95	8.7	2.1	0.8
	Surface	5	10	91	100	98	4.5	3.7	1.0
Clopyralid	Drinking	10	50	110	88	90	11.9	1.4	1.0
	Bottled	5	10	53	89	86	9.1	1.4	0.9
	Surface	5	10	109	114	140	10.0	1.4	0.6
Glyphosate	Drinking	10	50	89	106	83	6.3	2.3	1.3
	Bottled	10	50	66	108	105	14.4	1.7	3.4
	Surface	10	50	82	101	90	5.0	10.1	1.8

Cationic pesticides

Cationic pesticide	Structure*
Trimethylsulfonium (TMS)	<chem>C[S+](C)C</chem>
Morpholine	<chem>C1CCNCC1</chem>
Mepiquat	<chem>C1CC[N+](C)CC1</chem>
Chlormequat	<chem>C1CC[N+](C)CC1Cl</chem>
Diquat	<chem>C1=CN2C=CC=CC=C2N1</chem>
Paraquat	<chem>C1=CN=C(C=C1)C2=CC=CC=N2</chem>
ISTD d8-Paraquat	<chem>C1=CN=C(C=C1)C2=CC=CC=N2</chem>

*Trimethylsulfonium (TMS)
**SANTE accuracy limit of <5 ppm²³

Confirming	Accurate Mass (m/z)			Coef. of Determination (r^2)	LOD ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
	Reference	Measured	Accuracy (<5 ppm)**		
TMS*	62.019 61.011	77.0043 77.0043	—	0.989	0.14
Morpholine	70.066 68.050	88.0764 88.0763	-1.0 ppm	0.989	0.46
Mepiquat	98.097 58.066	114.1283 114.1280	-0.3 ppm	0.986	0.097
Chlormequat	124.070 58.066	122.0736 122.0736	—	0.987	0.089
Diquat	157.076 143.081	183.0920 183.0917	-0.3 ppm	0.980	1.1
Paraquat	185.107 171.092	186.1146 186.1157	+1.1 ppm	0.980	0.47
ISTD d8-Paraquat	97.5844 96.5797	97.0832 97.0829	-3.0 ppm	—	—

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Disinfection Byproducts in Drinking Water

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- Disinfection treatment is essential to eliminate waterborne disease-causing microorganisms
- Ozonation – bromate
- Chlorination (chlorine or chloramine)
 - Chlorite, chlorate
 - Trihalomethanes (THM) and haloacetic acids (HAAs)
- Highly regulated due to associated health issues
 - Chlorite: nervous system, affects fetal development, anemia
 - Bromate: carcinogenic
 - Chlorate: produce gastritis, blood diseases, and acute renal failure.
 - THM & HAAs: chronic exposure could increase risk of cancer
- Regulated under Safe Drinking Water Act
- EPA promulgated to the states

1ppb HAA standard, mixture of 9 HAAs

Method Detection Limits for HAAs by ICMS

Analyte	Calculated MDL (ppb)	EPA Method 557 MDL (ppb)	EPA Method 552.2 MDL (ppb)
MCAA	0.105	0.20	0.273
MBAA	0.104	0.064	0.204
DCAA	0.044	0.055	0.242
DBAA	0.021	0.015	0.066
BCAA	0.059	0.11	0.251
TCAA	0.033	0.090	0.079
BDCAA	0.141	0.050	0.091
DBCAA	0.214	0.041	0.468
TBAA	0.159	0.067	0.820
Dalapon	0.050	0.038	N/A
Bromate	0.059	0.020	N/A

Metabolomics

Diversity in structures and physical chemical properties

- Low molecular weight compounds, examples, amino acids, lipids, carbohydrates, nucleosides, hormones and derivatives
- No single analytical technique to measure entire metabolome
- Require multiple separations to capture entire metabolome
- Or specific separations to target certain chemical classes
- Complex samples and field
- Diverse and wide concentration range
- Limit of detection
- Isobaric, require separation

Diverse Physical Properties among Metabolites

Metabolites	Hydrophobic Chromatography	MS ionization
triglycerides		+
cholesterol esters		+
diacylglycerols		+
sphingomyelins		+
phosphatidylcholines		+
phosphatidylethanolamines		+
other phospholipids		+&-
fatty acids		-
eicosanoids & metabolites		-
bile acids		-
bilirubin		+ or -
amino acids, amines		+
organic acids		-
sugars		-
Other polar: e.g. purines & pyrimidines		-

Separation of 600 ppb of 49 Metabolomic Analytes

Peaks	
1. Lactate	33. trans-Aconitate
2. Shikimate	34. Ribulose 5-phosphate
3. Acetoacetate	35. D-Fructose 1,6 diphosphate
4. Acetate	36. D-Fructose 2,6 diphosphate
5. Formate	37. IMP/Dihydroxyacetone phosphate/
6. Pyruvate	38. CTP/Adenosine 5'-diphosphate
7. Chloride	38-40. Unknown
8. Uridine	41. PRPP
9. Unknown	42-43. ATP/ dGTP/GTP
10. Chloride	44-45. Unknown
11. Nitrite	46. GDP
12. Glucose 1-phosphate	47-49. Unknown
13. cAMP	
14. Methyilmalonate	
15. Succinate	
16. Carbonate	
17. Tartrate/Malonate	
18. Fumarate	
19. 2-Oxoglutarate	
20. Fructose 6-phosphate	
21. Maleate	
22. D-Glucose 6-phosphate	
23. Ribose 5-phosphate	
24. Adenosine 5'-monophosphate	
25. Unknown	
26. Sulfate	
27. 2-phosphoglycerate	
28. Phosphate	
29. Unknown	
30. Citrate	
31. Isocitrate	
32. cis-Aconitate	
& Phosphoenolpyruvate	

Column: AS11HC-4um. 0.4 mm
 Flow: 25 μ L/min plus 15 μ L/min methanol, 2 mM acetic acid
 Gradient: 2 mM KOH, 2-12 mM (0-13.5 min), 12-20 mM (13.5-22.5 min), 70 mM (22.5-31.5 min), 70 mM for 6 minutes, equilibrate at 2 mM for 7.5 min

Identification: Confidence from MS/MS and RT

- ✓MS/MS match with standard and library, but not able to differentiate them
- ✓RT by separation provides confirmative info for identification

Superior to HILIC and RP Chromatographic Methods

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IC has superior resolution and sensitivity to HILIC and RP

More Polar Metabolites in Oral Cancer Cell Lysates

ThermoFisher
SCIENTIFIC

IC-HRAM found twice as many polar metabolites

Glycomics

What role do glycans play in biotherapeutics?

- 70% of protein drug candidates in clinical development are glycosylated
- Many host-pathogen interactions occur using glycans (recognition, degradation, etc)
- Glycosylation affects:
 - Biological activity
 - Pharmacokinetics
 - Stability
 - Immunogenicity
- Glycosylation is the most common PTM (post translational modification) studied in biopharmaceuticals

Characterization of Glycosylation

Challenges in Carbohydrate Analysis

- Carbohydrates do not have a chromophore.
 - Alternative detection techniques are needed.
- Carbohydrates are highly polar, and very similar in structure.
 - Chromatographic separation of individual monosaccharides can be challenging.
 - Chromatographic separation of oligosaccharides based on glycosidic linkages can be challenging.

HPAE-PAD overcomes the challenges of carbohydrate analysis

Sources of Oligosaccharide Complexity

Different Monosaccharides:

Glucose N-Acetylglucosamine
Galactose
Gal β (1-4)GlcNAc
Mannose L-Fucose

Anomerism:

Gal α (1-3)GlcNAc
N-Acetylgalactosamine

Monosaccharide Sequence:

GalNAc-Gal-Glc
Gal-GalNAc-Glc

Branching:

Linkage:

Gal(1-3)GlcNAc
Gal(1-4)GlcNAc

Carbohydrate-MS Schematics

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- Detection of analytes with high specificity
 - to avoid co-elution interferences
 - to avoid background interferences
- Verification of unknowns

IC/MS of Sugar Alcohols and Mono- and Disaccharides Using IC/MS

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HAPE-PAD-MS for the structural characterization of label-free O-glycans

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Compositional identification of selected O-glycans released from a porcine gastric mucin type III

Peak #	RT (min)	Composition*	Observed m/z	Theoretical m/z	Mass accuracy (ppm)	Charge
1	5.13	Hex Fuc [HexNAc] ₁	733.2896	733.2884	1.64	1
2	5.83	Hex Fuc HexNAc	530.2080	530.2090	1.89	1
3	8.34	Hex Fuc [HexNAc] ₂	733.2891	733.2884	0.95	1
4	10.10	[Hex] ₂ Fuc [HexNAc] ₂	1098.4210	1098.4206	0.36	1
5	11.14	[Hex] ₂ Fuc [HexNAc] ₁	895.3425	895.3412	1.45	1
6	12.83	[Hex] ₂ [Fuc] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	1041.3987	1041.3992	0.48	1
7	13.41	[Hex] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	1155.4424	1155.4421	0.26	1
8	17.50	[Hex] ₂ Fuc [HexNAc] ₂	1098.4213	1098.4206	0.64	1
9	18.32	[Hex] ₂ [Fuc] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	1203.4508	1203.4520	1.00	1
10	27.78	[Hex] ₂ [Fuc] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	958.3604	958.3571	3.44	2
11	28.54	[Hex] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	1317.4910	1317.4949	2.96	1
12	28.88	[Hex] ₂ [Fuc] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	998.8695	998.8678	1.72	2
13	31.05	Neu5Ac [Hex] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂	1040.3793	1040.3788	0.49	1
14	34.65	Neu5Ac Hex Fuc HexNAc	821.3060	821.3045	1.83	1
15	38.22	N-glycan, hybrid, sulfated	852.2811	852.2848	4.34	2
16	39.63	[Hex] ₂ Fuc [HexNAc] ₂ -SO ₃	669.7120	669.7115	0.79	2
17	46.13	[Hex] ₂ [Fuc] ₂ [HexNAc] ₂ -SO ₃	1121.3568	1121.3559	0.78	1
18	53.34	Hex Fuc [HexNAc] ₂ -SO ₃	813.2459	813.2452	2.09	1

*Hex, Hexose; Fuc, Fucose; HexNAc, N-Acetylhexosamine; Neu5Ac, N-Acetylneuraminic acid

Figure 7. MS/MS spectra of two O-glycans observed in the negative ion mode: (a) Hex Fuc HexNAc, and (b) Neu5Ac [Hex]₂ [HexNAc]₂.

Figure 8. Synchronized ion chromatograms of structural isomers: (a) [Hex]₂ Fuc [HexNAc]₂, (b) Neu5Ac [Hex]₂ [HexNAc]₂, and (c) [Hex]₂ [Fuc]₂ [HexNAc]₂ SO₃.

33 APPLICATION NOTE 74042

Conclusions

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Benefits of Ion Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry

- IC vs. LC
 - Greater specificity and selectivity for ionic compounds
 - Metal-free flow path reduces fouling of ion-exchange columns
- On-line desalting for high ionic strength matrices
 - Reduces MS signal suppression and possible detector damage
- Analytes are provided in the ionic form needed for MS detection Many isobaric metabolites (e.g. sugar phosphates) have identical MS/MS, therefore chromatographic separation is necessary for identification and quantitation
- Ion Chromatography provides efficient and sensitive separation for polar metabolites using patented technology
- IC with High Resolution/Accurate Mass spectrometry using Orbitrap technology
 - 10- to 100-fold increase in sensitivity
 - Resolve many more isomers than RP & HILIC
 - Provides a superior and complementary method for small polar metabolites

<https://www.thermoFisher.com/it/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/ion-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-ic-ms.html>

THANK YOU

Extreme Chromatography Workshop

A meeting on next frontiers in analytical separation

Valentina Schiavo (Università di Torino)
Analysis of Underivatized Aminoacids in Food Matrices

ANALYSIS OF UNDERIVATISED AMINO ACIDS IN FOOD MATRICES

Valentina SCHIAVO

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Amino acids are one of the five big groups of primary metabolites. They can be found in biological fluids or tissues of animals and plants in two principal categories: essential and nonessential ones. Essential amino acids constitute approximately 20-37 % of the proteins in every organism. In food production, the attention is focused on the amino acids microbial catabolism that produces key flavor compounds in products such as cheese, wine, honey, and other fermented foodstuff. Beyond their contribute to food taste, amino acids have an important role in nutrition; therefore, analyses in this field are useful to characterize and valorize food matrices as a potential nutraceutical.

Essentially, amino acids can be analyzed to establish the amount of free fraction or to determinate the protein composition in different proteomics approach, after digestion. In literature numerous approaches were developed by derivatization prior to HPLC-based analysis. HPLC methods without derivatization are certainly simpler and faster. However, the intrinsic characteristics of these molecules are the wide range of chemical properties regarding their polarity and charge state.

For these reasons, a protocol avoiding derivatization is difficult to build and tune. Our work focuses on the investigation to obtain a method to successfully separate underivatized amino-acids and detect them by ESI MS to study the composition of some food supplements.

We first investigated an ion-pairing C18-based chromatography method which takes advantage of the ruggedness of the C18 column and the phenomenon of ion-pairing using perfluorinated acids to couple cationic groups of the analytes. This method was then compared to a HILIC phase: HILIC NH₂ column was able to separate the 20 main amino acids in a 22-minute run. However, the method showed some issues regarding peak duration, shape and co-elutions and a very high flow-rate is required to generate an acceptable peak symmetry. Given those problems, we tried a new and different type of column, the Raptor Polar X by Restek. Polar X use a hybrid mechanism to separate molecules, both HILIC and ion-exchanger. The results showed a good separation and a satisfactory peak shape with a generally lower column flow.

After tuning of gradient conditions, we applied the method for the quantitation and profiling of free and protein-generated amino-acids in different food matrices. We explored the amino acids profile of a vast range of food matrices, ranging from raw materials used for the nutraceutical market (the black garlic and *Galdieria sulphurea* dry powder) to valorizable waste products of the winemaking chain and food commercial supplements.

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IMaSS
Italian Mass Spectrometry
Society

ANALYSES OF UNDERIVATISED AMINO ACIDS IN FOOD MATRICES

Valentina Schiavo

Università di Torino

May 8th 2023 Extreme Chromatography Day

Dipartimento di Biotecnologie Molecolari e Scienze per la Salute

Introduction

FOOD METABOLOMICS

Aim

FOODSTUFFS

Introduction

DERIVATISED AAs Analysis

AQC

OPA

PITC

FMOC

DEEMM

Absorbance and Reflectance

Light wave based analysis

Volatilization

Gas chromatography

Methods

UNDERIVATISED AAs Analysis

RP C₁₈

A: H₂O HFBA 5 mM
B: ACN

HILIC NH₂

A: 90:10 H₂O : aqueous 200 mM ammonium formate (pH: 2.8)
B: 90:10 ACN: aqueous 200 mM ammonium formate (pH: 2.8)

Polar X

A: H₂O AF 0.5%
B: 9:1 ACN:H₂O + 20 mM ammonium formate (pH 3)

Methods

RP C₁₈

Raptor C₁₈ 150 x 3 mm 2.7 μm

A: H₂O HFBA 5 mM

B: ACN

Flow: 0.2 mL/min

Methods

HILIC NH₂

Luna NH₂ 150 x 2.1 mm 5 μm

A: 90:10 H₂O : aqueous 200 mM ammonium formate (pH: 2.8)

B: 90:10 ACN: aqueous 200 mM ammonium formate (pH: 2.8)

Flow: 0.8 mL/min

Methods

Polar X

Raptor Polar X 100 x 2.1 mm 2.7 μm

A: H₂O AF 0.5%

B: 9:1 ACN: Aqueous 20 mM ammonium formate (pH 3)

Flow: 0.3 mL/min

Methods

LCMS 8045

Interface Type:	ESI
Heating Gas Flow (L/min)	30
Interface Temperature (°C)	300
Desolvation Temperature (°C)	526
Drying Gas Flow (L/min)	10

Compound name:	Transition:
Phenylalanine	166>149; 166>120
Leucine	132>86
Isoleucine	132>86
Methionine	150>104; 150>133
Tyrosine	182>136; 182>149
Valine	118>72
Proline	116>70
Alanine	90>73; 90>44
Threonine	120>74
Glycine	76>30; 76>59
Serine	106>60
Arginine	175>70; 175>129
Histidine	156>110; 156>96
Lysine	147>110; 147>90
Glutamic Acid	148>84; 148>130
Cystine	241>152; 241>122
Aspartic Acid	134>74; 134>88
Thryptophan	205>146; 205>118
Betaine	118>58
Cysteine	122>75; 122>105

Results

RP C₁₈ ion-pairing

Results

RP C₁₈ ion-pairing

Results

RP C₁₈ ion-pairing

$$R = 1.18 \times \left(\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{W_{0.5h1} + W_{0.5h2}} \right)$$

R = 1.26

Results

HILIC NH₂

Results

Polar-X

Results

Polar-X, Rt/lipophilicity correlation

Compound name:	Rt	Log P	Log D _{5.5}
Tryptophan	2,6	1,04	-1,06
Phenylalanine	2,7	1,11	-1,45
Leucine	3,1	0,73	-1,86
Isoleucine	3,5	0,73	-1,86
Methionine	3,7	0,37	-1,92
Tyrosine	4,2	0,38	-2,23
Valine	4,7	0,2	-2,16
Proline	5,5	0,57	-2,76
Arginine	6,1	-1,79	-5,41
Histidine	6,2	-1,26	-3,77
Alanine	6,3	-0,68	-2,88
Threonine	6,4	-1,23	-3,33
Glycine	6,6	-1,03	-3,2
Lysine	6,65	-1,04	-4,76
Glutamine	6,65	-1,67	-3,89
Asparagine	6,7	-1,51	-3,83
Cystine	7,75	1,23	-3,38
Glutamic acid	8,3	-1,43	-4,77
Aspartic acid	9,5	-0,67	-4,3

Methods

Free vs protein AAs

- ✓ 100 mg sample
- ✓ 10 ml of 3:5:12 H₂O:CHCl₃:MeOH
- ✓ Ultrasound extraction
- ✓ Centrifugation and supernatant collecting (2mL)
- ✓ Addition of 900 µL CHCl₃ and 400 µL H₂O
- ✓ Phase separation and recovery of the upper layer
(aqueous phase)

- ✓ 100 mg sample
- ✓ 10 mL 6 N HCl
- ✓ 2h autoclavage for total digestion
- ✓ Solution filtration (0.22 µm)
- ✓ 1:5 dilution
- ✓ SCX SPE cleanup or further dilution to 0.01 N HCl

Methods

	SAMPLE	Free	Protein	Methods
Waste Winemaking Products		✓		Polar X
White Fresh vs Black Aged Garlic		✓	✓	HILIC NH2 RP C18
<i>Galdieria sulphurea</i> Dried Extract		✓	✓	HILIC Polar X

Results

HILIC NH₂

White Fresh vs Black Aged Garlic

Results

RP C₁₈ ion-pairing

Galdieria sulphurea
Dried Extract

Results

Polar-X

Waste Winemaking Products:
 FAE -> lees
 RAE -> stalks
 VAE -> pomaces

Conclusions

- ✓ Three HPLC-MRM methods have been evaluated and applied to different matrices
- ✓ An extraction method for free and protein AAs has been reported

- **C₁₈ ion-pairing** method shows the best peak shape and resolves well the leucine-isoleucine couple, however suffers of coelutions at dead time
- **HILIC NH₂** shows the highest RT for the first-eluting compound, suffers however of bad peak shape and duration, in addition most of peaks are eluting in a short range of time
- **Polar-X** shows an overall better separation for all the molecules comprising the Leu-Ile couple, in addition the method is capable of achieving the complete separation in the least of time.

Future Perspectives

- Ampliate the analytes panel
- Validate the methods on different matrices including clinical matrices (blood, marrow, tissue)

T H A N K S

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